

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF CONTEXTUALIZED LEARNING MATERIALS FOR ENGLISH 8

Razel R. Lining

English Department, Tigwi National High School, Torrijos, Marinduque, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15547596>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop and validate contextualized learning materials for English 8 to enhance student performance, address content and language gaps in existing resources, and support learners with limited access to technology. The researcher employed a descriptive-evaluative research design and adhered to the ADDIE model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation) to create structured and engaging materials. The study was conducted in Torrijos District, Marinduque, with 14 English teachers, three master teachers, one supervisor, and 30 Grade 8 students selected through purposive sampling. A standardized module evaluation checklist and a Likert-scale questionnaire were used to assess the contextualized learning materials regarding objectives, content, language, and assessment, obtaining Very Much Valid with a rating of 4.62, indicating high quality. A paired t-test shows that students' scores increased from 16.03 on the pre-test to 40.60 on the post-test, indicating that the contextualized learning materials for English 8 helped boost students' interest, comprehension, and academic performance. Based on the results, this study recommends the use of contextualized learning materials for English 8 as additional resources, supported by quality assurance, teacher orientation, responsible student use, continued development efforts, and further research for broader validation and application.

Keywords: *Develop, Validate, Contextualized Learning Materials, English, Academic Performance, Learners*

INTRODUCTION

English is a widely used language in education and research, providing access to a broad range of academic resources and facilitating global communication. Language abilities help students perform better in school in many areas and give them the capacity for critical thinking and analysis to grow as individuals. Izatullah et al. (2022) found that English proficiency is highly associated with academic success, with higher levels of competence linked to higher grade point averages (GPAs). Similarly, Aina et al. (2013) show a significant correlation between students' competence in English and their academic performance in science and technical education. However, learning English can be challenging, especially for those who are not native speakers.

In the Philippines, many students struggle with English because the structure and vocabulary differ significantly from that of Filipinos. According to Delos Reyes et al. (2023), these differences make it more challenging for students to comprehend English lessons. Around the world, students face similar problems in learning English, such as a lack of vocabulary, fear of speaking, and not enough practice (Rintaningrum et al., 2016). These challenges are exacerbated in the Philippines by poor reading comprehension results, as shown in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (2018).

In addition, the alarming revelation by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) that 18 million Filipino junior and senior high school graduates from 2019 to 2024 are “functionally illiterate” highlights a critical gap in the country’s basic education system, particularly in English language comprehension. Despite completing formal schooling, these students cannot reportedly read, understand, and make sense of simple texts, as emphasized during a Senate hearing led by Senator Sherwin Gatchalian. This situation underscores the urgent need for more effective, relevant, and context-based instructional materials that can enhance learners' reading comprehension and critical thinking skills. (Ramos, 2025).

Former DepEd Secretary Leonor Briones emphasized the importance of Self-Learning Modules (SLMs), especially for students who study independently. She noted that well-designed materials enable students to become more independent and continue learning even when face-to-face classes are not possible. However, many students still lack access to quality, relatable materials, especially those in remote areas.

Dechavez (2024) shared that using contextualized materials—materials designed to match students’ real-life experiences and local culture—can help learners understand better, especially in reading and comprehension. To address the learning crisis, the Department of Education (DepEd) developed programs such as the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) and the Learning Support Aide (LSA) Program. These were meant to help students continue learning through online and modular approaches.

In Marinduque, a small island province in the Philippines, many students live in far-flung and mountainous barangays. Some areas lack strong cellphone signals or internet access, rendering students unable to rely on online lessons or digital materials. In schools like Tigwi National High School, students depend on printed learning modules. However, many of the available modules are not localized—they use unfamiliar examples, settings, and language that students find hard to relate to. This gap between the content of the materials and the students' everyday experiences exacerbates the difficulty of learning English.

Although the DepEd has provided materials for English 8 from regional and central offices, there are still insufficient references. A need remains for materials that reflect learners' own experiences, language level, and cultural background. Many English lessons in the current modules are difficult to understand because they use examples or contexts that are unfamiliar to students living in rural or coastal areas. This hinders learners' ability to connect with what they are studying, affecting their comprehension and performance in English.

Moreover, the performance of Grade 8 students in English for the second quarter at Tigwi National High School has been consistently low over the past three school years: 2021-2022, 2022-2023, and 2023-2024, as shown by their mean percentage scores (MPS). The following were the MPS data for the previous three years: 58.64% for S.Y. 2021–2022, 69.27% for S.Y. 2022–2023, and 65.12% for S.Y. 2023–2024, all interpreted as average level. The specific competencies in which students performed poorly include:

- explaining visual-verbal relationships illustrated in tables, graphs, and information maps found in expository texts;
- using opinion-marking signals to express ideas;
- comparing and contrasting the presentation of the same topic in different multimodal texts;
- comparing and contrasting their own opinions with those presented in familiar texts; and
- recognizing positive and negative messages conveyed in a text.

According to the data, the performance of Grade 8 students in the English subject, particularly in the second quarter competencies, was consistently poor over three years. This was far from the target mastery and achievement level required by the Department of Education, which is 75%, interpreted as a “Moving Towards Mastery” level. The difference between the Grade 8 learners' performance and the target level of mastery was clear evidence that their learning concerns needed assistance. The data reveal that the Grade 8 students are not meeting the expected performance in the second-quarter learning competencies. This data analysis allowed the researcher to identify the essential learning competencies based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), which became the starting point of the study.

To address this, the researcher saw the need to develop contextualized English learning materials based on the MELCs for Grade 8. These materials aim to provide more relatable and meaningful content that matches the students' environment and learning

needs. The materials are also designed for easy use in communities with limited technology, making them practical and useful for learners in Tigwi National High School and other similar schools in Marinduque.

The primary objective of this study was to develop and validate contextualized learning materials that enhance students' understanding of second-quarter topics in English 8. By utilizing familiar settings, simple language, and culturally relevant examples, the materials are expected to improve students' performance in English and increase their enjoyment of the learning experience.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

English as a Learning Area in the Philippines

English and Filipino are two of the country's official languages. English is a fundamental learning subject in the Philippine education system due to its role as both a subject and a medium of instruction, as stated in the 1987 Philippine Constitution (Article XIV, Sections 6–7). This approach ensures that students learn both languages, enabling them to use them effectively in school and the workplace. English is taught starting in grade school and remains a core subject through high school and college. It is essential for more than just communication; it is the primary language used in subjects such as Science, Math, and Technology, which provides students with access to study resources and information from around the world.

Several government policies boost the importance of English in Philippine schooling. Executive Order No. 210 (2003) emphasizes the need to use English more as a language of instruction, enabling students to acquire sufficient proficiency to compete globally. Additionally, Republic Act No. 10533, also known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, has made English part of the K–12 education system. This makes reading, writing, and speaking even more essential.

Also, DepEd Order No. 74, s. In 2009, the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) framework was established. This framework utilizes students' home languages for early education, transitioning to English for higher grades. The strategy recognizes the importance of learning a language and helps students prepare for higher-level classes taught in English.

The research underscores the direct relationship between English proficiency and academic success. Aina et al. (2013) found that students with higher English proficiency perform better in subjects such as Science and Technical Education, as comprehension of complex concepts relies heavily on language skills. Similarly, Izatullah et al. (2022) revealed a significant correlation between students' English skills and their GPAs in higher education. This indicates the vital importance of English support classes in enhancing learning. For instance, students with difficulties in English may struggle to understand science or math terms or word problems, which can lower their overall grades. Conversely, students proficient in English can better understand and study subjects with extensive text, thereby improving their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

English's role in preparing people for work makes it even more important in school. Many industries in the Philippines, including business process outsourcing (BPO), tourism, and technology, require strong English communication skills. Employers prioritize applicants with high English proficiency, which is widely used in multinational companies and international trade. Thus, students who master English have better employment opportunities and can participate more effectively in global interactions.

Given its importance, developing contextualized learning materials for English education is essential. Studies, such as Saro (2023), suggest that contextualized materials—incorporating local culture, real-life experiences, and relatable scenarios—enhance student engagement and comprehension. For example, English learning materials that include Filipino folklore, current social issues, or real-world business scenarios make lessons more relevant and meaningful to students. This approach helps people learn languages more effectively and encourages them to think critically and appreciate other cultures.

In conclusion, English remains vital in the Philippine educational system because it enables students to excel academically, prepare for the workforce, and communicate effectively with people worldwide. Government policies, study results, and real-life scenarios demonstrate that English instruction needs to be more effective. Thus, developing and evaluating contextualized learning materials can help students learn more effectively, ensuring that English classes remain practical, efficient, and tailored to the needs of Filipino students.

English Proficiency and Academic Performance

Research has shown a strong connection between English language proficiency and academic achievement, particularly in subjects that demand higher-order thinking skills, such as science and technical education. A study by Aina et al. (2013) found that students with stronger English skills performed better in science classes, highlighting the essential role of language in comprehending and applying scientific concepts. The researchers emphasized that improving English instruction could enhance student outcomes in technical subjects. Similarly, Izatullah et al. (2022) confirmed a positive correlation between English proficiency and overall academic success at the college level. Their study showed that universities need language support programs because students who spoke and wrote English better did better in school. Rudd and Honkiss (2018) also investigated how college students' English skills affect their ability to do well in school. They discovered that students who spoke English less well had more trouble with homework and tests, especially those that required them to think critically and write in a complicated way. According to a study, universities should provide more language support services to help students do better in school and improve their language skills.

Challenges in Language Learning

Language learning can be challenging, especially for students learning a second language, because the vocabulary is different, they do not use the language much outside

of school, and they do not feel confident using it. Delos Reyes et al. (2023) examined the problems English-speaking students encounter when trying to learn Filipino in their study. They identified differences in vocabulary and a lack of opportunities to use the language outside of class as significant issues that hindered learning. Many students also did not have the confidence to participate and understand thoroughly. Delos Reyes et al. (2023) said that engaging and immersive learning methods could help students get around these problems by giving them more chances to use the language in real-life situations.

Education Policies and Learning Continuity

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused many problems for education systems around the world. As a result, governments and schools have had to come up with rules to make sure that students and teachers stay safe while still being able to learn. The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) for School Year 2020-2021 was made by the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines. This plan used a mix of learning methods, like modular, online, and TV-based teaching, to ensure that learning continued even during the pandemic. The DepEd also stressed helping students who do not have much access to technology. They knew that teachers and parents needed to be involved for distance learning to work (Department of Education, 2020). The Learning Support Aide (LSA) Program was also very helpful in leading students through their online and modular lessons. Pilot tests showed that LSAs were very important for getting kids interested, especially in areas where parents did not help out much. However, problems with funding, hiring, and teaching LSAs were found and could be fixed to make the program work better.

Modular Distance Learning

The Department of Education (DepEd) introduced modular distance learning (MDL) to maintain educational continuity and offer Filipino students top-notch training. When using distance learning as a mode of delivery, teachers and students are physically separated during instruction. This modality has three varieties: TV/Radio-Based Instruction, Online Distance Learning, and Modular Distance Learning (MDL) (Quinones, 2020).

In the Philippines, modular learning is the most popular type of distance learning. According to a Department of Education (DepEd) survey, parents preferred printed and digital modules over other learning modalities (Bernardo, n.d.). Online learning is less practical in rural areas where internet availability is limited, making this choice especially pertinent.

In the MDL framework, teachers play a crucial role in tracking students' progress. Students can request help from teachers through various communication channels, including email, phone calls, and instant messaging. Teachers also visit students' homes to provide assistance and remediation, ensuring accessibility.

Parents are vital partners in their children's education because formal education is now conducted at home. Home facilitators' primary responsibility is to direct and create a

disciplined learning environment (Manlangit et al., 2020). DepEd categorizes parents into three groups: Module-ator, Bundy-clock, and Home Innovator, recognizing their varied roles in modular learning. Parents oversee the gathering and submission of Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) from designated sites as Module-ators. As Bundy-Clock, they assist in controlling their child's study time to avoid cramming and guarantee that assignments are turned in on time. Finally, they establish a favorable learning environment as a Home Innovator by ensuring few distractions and sufficient ventilation and lighting.

One of the main advantages of modular training is the encouragement of independent learning. Nardo (2017) asserted that modules help students become more adept at self-study and take charge of their education. Through modular training, students progress at their own pace while refining their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Other benefits include enhanced adaptability to various learning styles, access to a broader range of educational resources, and greater flexibility for both teachers and students.

However, modular learning also has drawbacks. Students must be highly motivated and self-disciplined to complete their assignments independently. Creating modules requires more time and effort from teachers and staff, as well as significant administrative resources to monitor student development (Nardo, 2017). In addition, compared to traditional classroom settings, teachers in modular instruction receive fewer concrete rewards or feedback.

Despite its challenges, modular distance learning remains a vital alternative to traditional classroom instruction, ensuring ongoing education despite its limitations. Modular Distance Learning (MDL) supports the long-term development of Filipino students by promoting self-directed learning and engaging parents as active participants in their children's education.

Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs)

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted various sectors, including education. In response, the Department of Education (DepEd, 2020) remains committed to ensuring the continuity of quality basic education through the Sulong Edukalidad initiative. This effort aims to develop holistic Filipino learners equipped with 21st-century skills by making learning standards relevant and adaptable to the challenges posed by the pandemic.

The DepEd Bureau of Curriculum Development (DepEd, 2020) released the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) for nationwide implementation in School Year (SY) 2020-2021 to address these challenges. These competencies serve as the primary reference for schools, school division offices (SDOs), and regional offices (ROs) in determining and implementing appropriate learning delivery approaches based on local contexts and learner diversity. The MELCs eliminate the need for separate lists of learning competencies while allowing for enhancements and contextualization to support effective learning. Teachers are expected to prepare weekly Learning Activity Sheets (LAS),

participate in capacity-building programs, assist parents in facilitating home-based learning, prepare students for formal classes, and gather learner data to refine instruction.

The MELCs are categorized into essential and desirable competencies. Essential competencies provide students with the basic information and skills necessary to address real-life problems. Desirable competencies, on the other hand, enhance education without being essential. These skills are intended to be applicable in various learning situations, allowing them to be used beyond traditional classrooms. Furthermore, the emergence of MELCs is not just a reaction to the pandemic; it is the result of a curriculum review that began two years ago. With the help of educational experts, this review identified areas where the curriculum overlapped and became too crowded, leading to a simplified approach that concentrated on essential competencies. The Assessment Curriculum and Technology Research Centre (ACTRC) played a crucial role in this review and continues refining the MELCs beyond COVID-19.

The MELCs are structured based on several key characteristics: (a) alignment with national education standards, (b) integration of content across subjects, (c) applicability to real-life situations, (d) essentiality for students even if they discontinue schooling, and (e) exclusive to formal education. One thing that makes key competencies distinctive is their "endurance," meaning they are valuable in multiple tasks or courses of study. Research skills, reading comprehension, writing, reading maps, and testing hypotheses are important for career and lifelong learning. MELCs do not replace curriculum guides; instead, they are an additional tool teachers can use to satisfy instructional expectations efficiently. Another recommendation to field implementers is to contextualize MELCs to fit the requirements of students, instructors, and their learning settings.

The Basic Education – Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), which outlines measures to sustain education amid the pandemic, was introduced by the Department of Education (DepEd) in 2020 to support these efforts. The BE-LCP recommends delivering education while protecting the health and welfare of personnel, teachers, and students. It consists of programs like Brigada Eskwela and Oplan Balik Eskwela, school health standards requirements, and cooperative collaborations to improve educational adaptability. Adjusting the K–12 Curriculum to accommodate flexible learning delivery by including MELCs, aligning instructional materials, and changing policies is an important aspect of this plan. DepEd (2020) encourages educators in both public and private institutions to develop innovative and contextualized learning resources tailored to student needs. According to Section 10.3 of Republic Act No. 10533, the production and enhancement of educational materials must align with the curriculum and be adaptable to diverse learning contexts.

Through these initiatives, Filipino learners are assured of relevant, high-quality education despite the challenges posed by COVID-19. A follow-up issuance will provide additional guidance on MELC implementation and its role in the broader K-12 curriculum review.

Instructional Design

Effective learning is achieved through instructional design (ID), a methodical process that involves creating, implementing, and evaluating teaching tools and experiences. A structured framework helps teachers and instructional designers organize material, select the most effective teaching methods, and assess student progress. As a blueprint, an instructional design model shows the necessary steps to make learning experiences essential and enjoyable. Models like ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation) or Merrill's First Principles of Instruction help structure educational programs to enable students to remember what they have learned, become more interested in learning and develop their skills in various settings, such as classrooms, online courses, and corporate training. By following instructional design principles, educators can create effective, learner-centered lesson plans that meet specific educational goals and encourage valuable learning (Davis, 2013).

The ADDIE Design Model

ADDIE stands for "Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate." In instructional design, it is an acknowledged fact that this framework provides authenticity, showing how to set up beneficial learning opportunities in a planned and logical manner. This framework facilitates the sharing of information, making it easier for experts to share their knowledge. Experts can apply it to various learning products, including coaching sessions, lectures, online and offline training, and informational publications.

The ADDIE model consists of five stages:

- Analysis: Determines the contextual elements and learning requirements.
- Design: Creates learning goals and methods for evaluation.
- Development: Produces and puts together educational resources.
- Implementation: Gives students access to educational materials.
- Evaluation: Determines whether the lesson is practical and implements the required changes.

Analysis

Every step that follows is built upon the analysis phase. Instructional designers discover performance gaps, set targets, and evaluate the learning environment. This entails conducting needs, job, and task analyses to determine instructional requirements and understand learner characteristics. Task lists and instructional goals are among the outputs from this phase that help guide the design stage (Lockee, 2019).

Design

Based on the results of the analysis phase, a thorough instructional approach is created during the design phase. This includes selecting instructional methodologies, establishing learning objectives, determining evaluation techniques, and creating a

course plan. The objectives are to enhance learner engagement and match instructional materials to intended learning outcomes (Lockee, 2019).

Development

The Development phase involves developing and assembling instructional materials, as outlined in the design phase. Along with printed materials, such as textbooks and training guides, this may also include creating multimedia materials, including e-learning modules, video tutorials, and interactive simulations. Before being fully implemented, materials are frequently evaluated and improved to guarantee efficacy (Lockee, 2019).

Implementation

Learners receive instructional material during implementation in various contexts, including blended learning, online learning environments, and classrooms. Currently, the purpose is to engage students in productive activities that help them learn more effectively. To facilitate students' understanding and retention, teachers need to prepare effectively, focus on the students, and employ appropriate instructional methods (Lockee, 2019).

Evaluation

The effectiveness and efficiency of the learning experiences and instructional materials are assessed during the evaluation phase. Formative and summative assessments are integral to the evaluation process, which occurs during the instructional design phase. The summative evaluation examines the effectiveness of the implementation. In contrast, the formative evaluation identifies areas for improvement as they are being developed. The outcomes of this step determine the necessary changes, ensuring that instructional design continues to improve (Lockee, 2019).

Figure 1 illustrates the ADDIE framework, a method for ensuring that learning tools are well-designed and effective.

Figure 1

The ADDIE Model

Source: <https://elearningindustry.com/lets-talk-addie-it-still-matters>

Self-Learning Modules (SLMs)

Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) are instructional materials designed to facilitate independent learning, helping students acquire specific content or skills without requiring direct interaction with a teacher. They have become particularly useful in distance learning environments, especially during emergencies like the COVID-19 pandemic, when traditional classroom learning is disrupted. Modular learning was widely implemented in the Philippines when face-to-face classes were suspended due to the pandemic (Santos, 2020).

Self-Learning Modules typically consist of several key components that guide the learner through the learning process. The introduction and learning objectives section outlines the goals and objectives of the module, giving students a clear idea of what they are expected to learn and achieve (Gueta & Janer, 2021). The lesson content forms the core of the module, providing explanations, examples, images, videos, and other resources to help students understand the topic (Gueta & Janer, 2021). Meanwhile, activities and exercises are tasks or assignments that allow students to apply what they have learned and reinforce their understanding of the material. These can include quizzes, reflection questions, or practice problems (Lutching, 2024). The instructions and guidance section provides clear directions on approaching the content, activities, and

exercises and may include tips, strategies, or additional resources for in-depth study (Lumapenet, 2022). Assessment and feedback are included at the end of the module to evaluate whether the student has achieved the intended learning outcomes, helping them understand areas needing improvement (Lumapenet, 2022). Some modules also provide references or further reading for students seeking a deeper understanding of the topic (Rico & Mendoza, 2021).

In addition, SLMs differ depending on their format, level, and subject matter. Printed modules are traditional, paper-based materials distributed to students as booklets, worksheets, or printed handouts (Gueta & Janer, 2021). Due to technological advancements, digital modules, such as PDFs, interactive websites, or online platforms that allow students to interact with material on their devices (Santos, 2020), are now widely available. Furthermore, audio-visual modules incorporate multimedia elements, including videos or audio files, to enhance the learning experience, particularly for visual or auditory learners (Gueta & Janer, 2021).

Also, SLMs offer numerous benefits. Flexibility is a significant advantage since students can study at their own pace, rereading or skipping content as needed, which is especially beneficial for pupils with diverse levels of comprehension (Lutching, 2024). They also promote accessibility, as they can be used in remote or underserved areas where traditional face-to-face teaching is not feasible, ensuring continued education even during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic (Santos, 2020). Independence is another advantage, as SLMs promote self-discipline, motivation, and independent learning, allowing students to develop self-management capacity as they go through the modules. Additionally, variation enables students to focus on areas that need improvement, modifying the learning experience to their specific needs (Lutching, 2024).

However, SLMs also come with challenges. One such issue is the lack of immediate feedback, as students learning independently may struggle to understand concepts without direct guidance from a teacher (Gueta & Janer, 2021). Motivation issues can also arise, as some students may struggle to stay motivated or procrastinate when completing modules (Lutching, 2024). Another difficulty is the limited interaction with teachers and peers, as SLMs do not facilitate collaboration or clarification of concerns (Rico & Mendoza, 2021). Additionally, problems arise with material quality, as poorly designed modules may result in confusion or ineffective learning (Gueta & Janer, 2021).

Despite this, SLMs have become an integral part of the education system in the Philippines, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. The Department of Education (DepEd) adopted modular learning to deliver education when face-to-face classes were suspended (Santos, 2020). These modules were designed for students to use at home, with the assistance of parents or guardians (Gueta & Janer, 2021). Various government and private initiatives have worked on developing and distributing SLMs, which are aligned with the curriculum standards set by DepEd and cover subjects ranging from basic education to senior high school (Rico & Mendoza, 2021).

According to research, SLMs can increase student performance if they are well-designed and supported by appropriate mentoring. They have been especially valuable in ensuring that students continue their education in the face of natural disasters or pandemics (Lutching, 2024). Nevertheless, issues like the quality of materials, distribution challenges, and the need for supplemental support (such as online consultations with teachers or community-based learning centers) are still being addressed to improve the overall effectiveness of SLMs (Lumapenet, 2022). Moreover, learning modules have enhanced students' achievement and motivation toward a subject. Estremera, Hizon, and Claridades (2017) emphasized that instructional materials should meet quality and acceptability standards to be considered valid and effective. Similarly, Estremera et al. (2017) and Gianan (2016) highlighted that a well-developed learning module should comprehensively outline learning objectives, content, experiences, and outcomes while addressing students' knowledge, skills, and conceptual understanding.

Contextualized Learning Materials

Contextualized learning materials (CLMs) enable learners to learn by tailoring to their actual situations of interest, needs, and situations. These resources make learning more applicable, engaging, and relevant by using real-life examples that provide comprehensive information in the classroom. The Department of Education (DepEd, 2020) says that learning modules should be contextualized to correspond with the backgrounds of students, the circumstances, and scenarios from daily life. This helps ensure that the lessons are relevant and valuable so students can apply what they learn in school.

Contextualized learning resources are important because they improve the effectiveness of the learning process. According to Dale's Cone of Experience, learning materials improve students' understanding of topics by providing authentic experiences and making instruction more engaging (DepEd, 2020). Contextualized materials engage students in ways that a standard, comprehensive curriculum may not, as they represent students' experiences. By using local examples, culturally appropriate stories, and scenarios that reflect learners' contexts, educators can develop deeper connections and improve students' motivation and comprehension.

Instructional modules include essential parts such as a cover page, title page, introductory message, instructional tasks, answer keys, and references. The cover page often features the title, grade level, and school logo, while the back cover contains copyright and publication information. The first part of the module outlines the learning competencies, providing clear directions for use to ensure that students and educators understand the module's objectives and how to interact with the materials (DepEd, 2020). Macarandang (2009) defined these modules as self-instructional tools that allow students to learn autonomously, at their own pace, and at leisure.

The contextualization of instructional modules can improve the learning experience by connecting content with students' real-world experiences. Bringas (2014), DepEd Order No. 35 (2016), and UNESCO-IBE (2024) assert that contextualized

education enhances the relevance and engagement of the learning experience. This strategy allows students to see how their teachings are applied immediately, which can help them grasp and remember concepts more effectively. According to Rivet and Krajcik (2008) and Baker et al. (2009), contextualized learning improves knowledge retention, conceptual understanding, and assessment performance.

Using a variety of instructional resources also enhances the entire learning process. Ogaga and Wallace (2016) stated that utilizing various teaching tools is crucial for meeting class standards and ensuring students learn more effectively. Contextualized learning resources are especially effective at engaging students in physics, mathematics, and social studies, where real-world applications help them understand abstract concepts (Claridades, 2017; Gianan, 2016). Furthermore, novel learning aids such as pop-up books are highly beneficial in engaging students and promoting learning outcomes (Sales, 2020).

Research supports the usefulness and effectiveness of contextualized learning materials in enhancing academic performance. Cubillas (2018) and Torre Franca (2017) found that well-designed instructional modules significantly improved student learning outcomes. Aguinaldo and Domingo (2021) also found that contextualized learning modules helped students become more skilled in mathematics and made the material more culturally relevant. Similarly, Abdelmohsen (2020) demonstrated that instructional modules significantly increase students' critical thinking and writing skills, as proven by pretest-posttest results.

Instructional modules follow established procedures, such as ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation), ensuring that materials are generated systematically and tailored to student needs. Widyastuti and Susiana (2019) and Permanasari (2018) proved the usefulness of instructional modules by aligning them with student needs and learning objectives.

Finally, contextualized instructional materials contribute positively to the quality of education by making learning more relevant, engaging, and effective. They consider not only what students need to learn but also their cultural and environmental contexts, which leads to better learning outcomes. Using these kinds of tools helps bridge the gap between what is learned in school and how it is applied in the real world, leading to improved grades, critical thinking skills, and cultural awareness.

Development of Learning Materials

Making new learning tools is crucial to getting students interested in learning and helping them improve in school. It is essential to have contextualized and localized learning tools because they allow students to connect their learning and their own lives and surroundings. This makes them more motivated and helps them understand better. Capuyan (2021) looked at how well-contextualized learning activity sheets (LAS) worked for science students in the 7th grade. The study showed that students who used the contextualized LAS were more interested and understood what they were reading than

students who used traditional textbooks. This shows how important it is to use localized information in science classes. Using the same ADDIE model, Jandulong (2024) created and tested a Combinatorics and Probability program for 10th graders. Expert validation and pre-and post-test data showed that the module greatly impacted how well students did on tests, with 87% doing exceptionally well. For example, these findings show that contextualized learning materials can help students improve math. In a different study, Givera (2023) conducted a study focusing on the creation and validation of contextualized supplementary worksheets for Grade 8 English students. The research emphasized the importance of aligning instructional materials with learners' cultural backgrounds and real-life experiences to enhance engagement and comprehension. The study also highlighted the significance of evaluating the materials' validity in terms of content, language, and assessment components, ensuring they meet educational standards and effectively support learning objectives.

A study published in the *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies* examined the impact of contextualized learning materials on students' reading skills and comprehension levels (Dinoy, 2024). The findings revealed a significant improvement in students' performance, with a notable mean score difference between the pretest and posttest results. This underscores the effectiveness of contextualized materials in enhancing learners' academic performance, directly addressing the fourth research question regarding the impact of such materials on students' learning outcomes.

Pacao and Pandes (2025) developed and evaluated contextualized guided-audio visual materials (C-GAME) for Grade 8 English learners at Lalawigan National High School. Utilizing a descriptive-inferential-evaluative research design, the study involved 63 Grade 8 students and 6 expert evaluators, including English teachers and ICT coordinators. The materials were assessed using the Department of Education's Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) evaluation tool. Findings indicated that the C-GAME materials were highly acceptable in terms of content quality, instructional quality, and technical quality. Moreover, there was a significant improvement in students' academic performance after using the materials, demonstrating their effectiveness in enhancing learning outcomes in English 8.

Lopez and Dizon (2022) created and evaluated a set of context-based reading modules specifically for Grade 8 English learners in a Philippine secondary school. Employing a descriptive-evaluative research design, they (1) crafted learning objectives tied to local themes, (2) developed content and language scaffolds reflecting students' daily experiences, (3) designed formative and summative assessments, and (4) packaged the modules with culturally familiar graphics. A panel of five content and language experts rated the materials on objectives, content accuracy, linguistic suitability, and assessment quality using a standardized checklist. Subsequently, a pilot implementation with 40 Grade 8 learners showed a statistically significant increase in posttest scores over pretest results, confirming both the validity and instructional impact of the materials (Lopez & Dizon, 2022).

Capuyan (2021) utilized the ADDIE model to develop and evaluate reading modules for Grade 8 students in the Philippines. First, he reviewed student results and spoke with teachers and learners to pinpoint reading and vocabulary gaps. He then established goals based on local themes, such as folktales and community events. Three modules were made, each with activities before reading, familiar stories, and tasks afterward (summaries, journals, and vocabulary exercises). Six experts—English teachers and specialists—reviewed the modules and rated them highly for their goals, content, language, and assessments. Finally, 30 students used the modules for four weeks, and their reading scores improved significantly, showing that the materials were effective and culturally relevant.

Assessment and Instructional Module Design

Ensuring that instructional modules work effectively is essential for keeping students engaged and boosting their academic success. Studies have shown that students are more likely to remember information and be motivated when it is linked to real-life events. Perin (2011) examined how contextualized learning makes lessons more interesting by relating them to real-life events. According to the study, students who had lessons rich in context remembered information better and were more eager to learn. The Department of Education – Schools Division Office of Baguio City (2020) also advised creating suitable learning modules, focusing on essential components such as content structure, technical requirements, and assessment. The DepEd aimed to improve the design and delivery of learning materials to encourage students to become more involved and understand the material better by reviewing existing lessons.

Validation and Quality of Learning Materials

It is essential to ensure that learning materials are helpful, accurate, and meet educational standards through the validation method. Studies have shown that having clear learning goals and visual tools to help students understand is crucial, especially for younger students or those who learn best in specific ways. Moss and Brookhart (2019) discussed the importance of learning goals in helping students learn. They discovered that students did better when lessons had clear and understandable learning goals. Their study demonstrated that setting clear goals is an essential part of the learning process. Varthana (2021) also found that visual aids are invaluable for learning, particularly for younger children or individuals who learn best by seeing things. The research found that using visual aids helped students understand complex ideas and retain information more effectively.

Revisions and Enhancements of Learning Materials

It is essential to keep learning tools up-to-date and useful by revising and improving them. Contextualization is a key part of ensuring that learning tools meet the needs of students and are also interesting and motivating. According to Kuncoro (2022), contextualized learning tools greatly impacted how well 7th graders could read. The study found that students did much better on reading tasks when the materials were made to fit

their cultural and social backgrounds. Similarly, Lardizabal et al. (2023) investigated how contextualized materials could enhance schoolwork. The research showed that students who used localized materials did better on tests and participated more in class talks. This indicates that contextualization can keep students interested and help them learn more effectively. Gonzales (2023) also worked on creating and evaluating regional extracurricular activities for Araling Panlipunan 10. The study confirmed that contextualization is essential for improving educational results. It showed that expert validation and student feedback helped make the materials more transparent and relevant.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to develop and validate the contextualized learning materials for English 8.

Specifically, it is expected to answer the following questions:

1. How were the contextualized learning materials for English 8 developed in terms of:
 - 1.1 Learning Objectives;
 - 1.2 Content;
 - 1.3 Language;
 - 1.4 Assessment; and
 - 1.5 Layout and Packaging?
2. What is the validity level of the contextualized learning materials for English 8 as evaluated by the validators in terms of:
 - 2.1. Learning Objectives;
 - 2.2. Content;
 - 2.3. Language; and
 - 2.4. Assessment?
3. What are the validators' feedback and suggestions for enhancing the contextualized learning materials for English 8?
4. How do contextualized learning materials for English 8 affect the learners' academic performance, as reflected in the pretest and posttest results?
5. From the validation made, what enhanced contextualized learning material could be developed by the researcher?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-evaluative research design which was appropriate for assessing the quality and effectiveness of instructional materials while also providing a detailed description of their features and implementation. This research design is used to gather objective data about a specific educational product and evaluate

it based on set criteria, such as content accuracy, appropriateness, clarity, and alignment with learning outcomes (Calderon & Gonzales, 2011).

Following a structured and sequential approach, the ADDIE model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation) served as the framework for this process. The learning objectives, target audience, and available resources were examined in the analysis phase. During the design process, the content was chosen and organized to meet the needs of the learners. In the development phase, the learning materials were created emphasizing selected learning competencies and objectives, essential information, appropriate language, and suited evaluation tasks. The developed contextualized learning was given to validators for expert validation during implementation. Lastly, during the evaluation phase, the contextualized learning materials were assessed using evaluation criteria to determine how well they established learning objectives, chose relevant language and content, and constructed assessment activities.

A survey questionnaire employing a Five-Point Likert scale and a checklist format was used to collect feedback, with experts' suggestions and recommendations recorded and documented. The data gathered were analyzed and interpreted using appropriate statistical methods.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the District of Torrijos, Province of Marinduque, specifically in seven secondary schools: Malibago National High School, Tigwi National High School, Maranlig National High School, Sibuyao National High School, Poctoy National High School, Bonliw National High School, and Matuyatuya National High School.

These schools were chosen because the researcher is an English 8 teacher at Tigwi National High School, where the issues of insufficient learning materials and the lack of textbooks for English 8 are prevalent. Furthermore, these schools serve communities in remote areas with limited access to electricity and the Internet, and students who rarely travel beyond their local communities have little experience with digital learning tools. As a result, they rely mostly on printed materials, such as modules, worksheets, and textbooks provided by the central office. This scenario makes it difficult for students to access other educational opportunities, highlighting the need for learning materials that are suitable and relevant to their local context.

Figure 4 shows a map of the Torrijos District, marking the locations of these seven high schools.

Figure 4

Map of the Province of Marinduque highlighting the Municipality of Torrijos

Source: Google Maps App

Research Population and Sample

Purposive sampling was used to select respondents qualified to validate the developed contextualized learning materials, as they had over five years of experience, knowledge, and expertise in teaching high school students. Fourteen English teachers, three English master teachers, and one English supervisor were among the respondents; they were all selected to offer a comprehensive assessment of the contextualized learning materials for English 8. Each of the seven schools had two English teacher respondents, making a total of 14 English teachers. Since there is no English Master Teacher in the Torrijos District, the researcher selected master teachers from the Boac and Gasan Districts with experience teaching English 8.

Moreover, Grade 8 students were also part of the study, as the contextualized learning materials were designed for them. A class of 30 Grade 8 students from Tigwi National High School utilized the materials to evaluate the impact on student performance.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a standardized Module Evaluation Checklist, adapted from a previous study by Gueller Dee V. Salazar, conducted in the same institution, to gather relevant data for this study. Specifically, the researcher employed a checklist-based questionnaire developed by Salazar (2018) to assess the content validity of the

contextualized learning materials regarding learning objectives, content, language, and assessment. Salazar (2018) based the evaluation instrument on the Department of Education's (DepEd) issued guidelines for the development and evaluation of self-learning modules (SLMs), specifically the DepEd Quality Assurance (QA) Tool for Self-Learning Modules. This tool outlines standards for evaluating instructional materials in terms of the clarity and alignment of objectives, content accuracy and relevance, language appropriateness, and the quality of assessment activities.

The checklist was divided into four sections: (a) learning objectives, evaluated based on five key characteristics; (b) module content, assessed using ten specific criteria; (c) language used, measured against five characteristics; and (d) assessment activities, evaluated using ten listed criteria related to assessment and evaluation. Additionally, the questionnaire included a feedback and comments section, allowing respondents to provide suggestions and insights on the developed printed learning materials.

Data Gathering Procedure

To conduct the study, the researcher began by analyzing the Mean percentage scores (MPS) for the past three years in the second quarter English examinations of Grade 8 students. This analysis revealed consistently low performance, which highlighted the need for more effective instructional materials. From this, the researcher identified the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) which served as the foundation for developing contextualized English modules. These competencies became the starting point for developing learning objectives, content, and assessment activities.

After developing the contextualized learning materials, the researcher sent a request letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of Marinduque in Boac through the Records Office, seeking permission to carry out the research in public high schools, specifically in the Torrijos District. After receiving the approval letter, the researcher was advised to obtain additional permission from the Public Schools District Supervisors overseeing the schools where the study would take place and from which the respondents would be selected. The researcher complied with this requirement.

Also, the researcher sought authorization from Mr. Gueller Dee V. Salazar to adapt the instrument employed in his 2018 study to validate a developed module. Once approval was granted, with authorization from the Division Superintendent and the Public Schools District Supervisors, the researcher prepared formal request letters for the school principals where the respondents were teaching. Along with the letters, printed copies of the contextualized learning materials were provided to the validators, and a checklist was created to assess the learning materials based on specific criteria. These learning materials and checklists were personally distributed to respondents in the seven high schools: Malibago National High School, Tigwi National High School, Maranlig National High School, Sibuyao National High School, Poctoy National High School, Bonliw National High School, and Matuyatuya National High School. Additionally, the materials were also distributed to two master teachers from Marinduque National High School and one master teacher from Bangbang National High School.

The respondents were given one to two weeks to complete the questionnaire. After this period, the researcher collected the completed checklists from the respective school principals' offices and consolidated the data. Additionally, in-person interviews were conducted to further validate the responses gathered through the checklist. Once all the necessary data were retrieved, they were encoded, organized, and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. The feedback and suggestions from the validators were also carefully considered when revising and improving the contextualized learning materials. The final version of the materials was then pilot-tested in the teaching-learning process with 30 students at Tigwi National High School. To measure their effectiveness, the researcher administered pretests and posttests for the second quarter to assess the impact of the learning materials on learners' performance. Based on the validation process, feedback, and pilot testing, the researcher developed an enhanced version of the contextualized learning materials for English, which served as the study's final output.

Data Analysis Procedure

To begin the process, the researcher conducted a data analysis to have thorough review on performance trends in English 8 for the second quarter over the past three school years at Tigwi National High School. The Mean percentage scores (MPS) from the second quarterly test were collected and examined. After analyzing the MPS, it remained in the "Average" category and continued to fall short of the target mastery level, which is "Moving Towards Mastery." This indicated that students consistently struggled with the learning competencies in English 8 during the second quarter. The second quarter competencies in which students performed poorly are the following: explaining visual-verbal relationships illustrated in tables, graphs, and information maps found in expository texts; using opinion-marking signals to express ideas; comparing and contrasting the presentation of the same topic in different multimodal texts; comparing and contrasting their own opinions with those presented in familiar texts; and recognizing positive and negative messages conveyed in a text.

Based on the identified learning gaps, the researcher designed contextualized learning materials tailored to the learners' prior knowledge, cultural background, and language proficiency. Specific objectives were set for the most challenging competencies, with content chosen from familiar topics, written in age-appropriate language. Assessments were aligned with learning goals, and the layout and packaging were designed to be visually engaging using Canva.

The learning materials, consisting of 92 pages printed on A4 bond paper, were validated by English supervisors, master teachers, and classroom teachers. They evaluated the materials based on the clarity of objectives, content accuracy, appropriateness of language, and the effectiveness of assessment tasks. Their feedback was coded and thematically analyzed, and revisions were made to enhance the materials' quality.

The revised contextualized learning materials were then pilot tested with 30 Grade 8 students. A 50-item pretest was administered before the materials were used, and a

posttest was conducted afterward. After being subjected to statistical treatment, the contextualized learning materials were found to be significant, as evidenced by the high difference in scores between the pretest and posttest. This indicates that the contextualized learning materials effectively addressed learners' needs, leading to better engagement and comprehension, as the content was meaningfully connected to their everyday experiences.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data obtained from the validation questionnaires was tallied, organized, and subjected to statistical treatment to simplify the presentation, analysis, and interpretation. Statistical tools, such as percentages and computations, were applied to address the stated problem in Chapter I.

A Likert scale with weights of 5 as the highest and 1 as the lowest was used to ensure respondents' objective evaluation of the different indicators being measured. It also presented the verbal interpretation of each value range using the Likert scale from Very Much Valid to Not Valid.

The data from the instruments were analyzed through a thorough statistical analysis to assess the effectiveness of the contextualized learning materials and their impact on the students' academic performance in English 8. A Likert Scale was used to evaluate the validity of the materials; each of the four components (learning objectives, content, language, and assessment) was assessed independently, and validators rated indicators like these on a scale of 1 to 5, where one means "not valid" and five means "very much valid." After keeping track of how many times each answer was given, the mean score for each part was calculated. This gave the validators a clear numerical breakdown of how each part looked when examined, which let them thoroughly assess its validity. A qualitative analysis was conducted on the validators' comments, recommendations, and quantitative data. Using coding and thematic analysis, these replies were classified into common themes. Recurring themes and comments were found through this method, and these were then combined to guide changes and enhancements to the contextualized learning resources.

A paired t-test was used to evaluate the impact of contextualized learning materials on students' academic performance. The pretest and posttest scores were compared to ascertain whether there was a statistically significant improvement in students' performance after using the materials. SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software was used to perform the paired t-test, a valid statistical technique for comparing two related samples. Because of its accuracy and dependability in data processing, this program is frequently used to ensure that test findings are valid and appropriately interpreted. The study thoroughly assessed the validity and effectiveness of the learning materials using a combination of quantitative and qualitative analysis

The statistical scale values used to measure the validity rating of each element are as follows:

- 4.20 – 5.0 - Very Much Valid
- 3.40 – 4.19 - Much Valid
- 2.60 – 3.39 - Moderately Valid
- 1.80 – 2.59 - Least Valid
- 1.00 – 1.79 - Not Valid

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter gives the findings based on the data collected on the variables studied. The data is presented and interpreted in each of the problems stated in Chapter I.

Research Question 1. Development of Contextualized Learning Materials for English 8

Before developing the contextualized learning materials for English 8, the researcher assessed the mean percentage scores (MPS) of students in English during the second quarter over the past three school years at Tigwi National High School. The MPS were as follows: 58.64% in S.Y. 2021–2022, 69.27% in S.Y. 2022–2023, and 65.12% in S.Y. 2023–2024. These scores fall under the “average” level and remain below the DepEd’ target of 75%, which is classified as “moving towards mastery.” This consistent gap in performance indicated that Grade 8 students need support in their learning. Consequently, the researcher figured out that the development of contextualized learning materials was needed. The learning needs of Grade 8 students were taken into consideration when developing the learning materials, ensuring that they were appropriately suited to their actual competency levels.

The contextualized learning materials for English 8 were developed in terms of learning objectives, content, language, assessment, and layout and packaging.

Learning Objectives

After noting that Grade 8 students struggled with the second-quarter competencies as reflected in the MPS over the past three years, the researcher determined the second-quarter competencies using the MELCs, a set of essential skills and knowledge outlined in the curriculum provided by the Department of Education.

Table 1 displays the second-quarter MELCs for English 8, which the researcher used as a guide for developing the contextualized learning materials.

Table 1*Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in English 8 for the Second Quarter*

Quarter	Grade Level Standards	Most Essential Learning Competencies	Duration	Code
Q2	The learner demonstrates communicative competence through their understanding of Afro-Asian Literature and other text types, allowing them to appreciate Philippine Culture and different countries more deeply.	Explain visual-verbal relationships illustrated in expository texts' tables, graphs, and information maps.	Week 1-2	EN8SS-Ile-1.2
		Use opinion-marking signals to share ideas.	Week 3-4	EN8RC-Ila-10
		Compare and contrast the presentation of the same topic in different multimodal texts.	Week 5-6	EN8VC-Ilg-15
		Compare and contrast your own opinions with those presented in familiar texts	Week 7	EN8VC-Ili-15
		Recognize positive and negative messages conveyed in a text	Week 8	EN8VC-Ila17

The researcher conducted a data analysis of the lesson objectives from her previous year's second-quarter classes in English 8. She examined the Index of Mastery (IM) for each lesson objective to determine whether the learning objectives were achieved or if there was a need for intervention. All lesson objectives that showed low mastery levels—those falling below the 80% standard—were identified and listed. These specific objectives were then prioritized for inclusion in the development of contextualized learning materials aimed at addressing the learning gaps of Grade 8 students.

After identifying the specified learning objectives, the researcher divided the larger objectives into more manageable, specific learning objectives, skills, or attitudes the students are expected to acquire. For instance, *analyze* was reworded to *identify*; *synthesize* was changed to *transfer*; *evaluate* was revised to *distinguish*; *construct* became *express*; *extract* turned to *interpret*; *analyze* was changed to *compare and contrast*; and *determine* was modified to *identify*.

Moreover, the learning objectives were then developed by the researcher using Bloom's taxonomy, which was divided into six categories, ranging from basic knowledge recall to higher-order thinking abilities, including evaluation and creation. To encourage in-depth understanding, the researcher ensured that learning objectives addressed a variety of cognitive levels. Specific and meaningful verbs that characterize observable

behaviors were used to convey each learning objective. The researcher also ensured that the objectives followed a logical sequence, progressing from lower-order thinking skills (LOTS) to higher-order thinking skills (HOTS). Action verbs like identify, transfer, interpret, classify, recognize, express, write, and distinguish were used to target lower-order thinking skills. Meanwhile, verbs like compare, contrast, and create were used to address higher-order thinking skills. This arrangement promotes cognitive development by progressively raising the difficulty of learning tasks. The learning objectives were also logically organized, enabling consistency and progression from basic concepts and skills to more challenging tasks.

The researcher ensured that every objective was reachable within the scope of the contextualized learning materials and aligned with the target learning competencies using the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). Each newly formulated objective was carefully reviewed against the DepEd’s MELCs to ensure its relevance. The researcher also ensured that no objective exceeded the coverage of the target second-quarter topics.

Lastly, the researcher reviewed the specified learning goals several times to ensure they satisfied the students' needs and the target learning competencies. Based on the feedback provided by the validators' responses, the researcher made necessary revisions to the objectives.

Content

The researcher carefully analyzed the identified learning competencies and specified learning objectives to determine the fundamental concepts and skills that needed to be addressed in the contextualized learning materials. Using the DepEd’s MELCs as a guide, the researcher selected key topics that matched the required skills and knowledge for Grade 8 English learners in the second quarter.

To ensure the contents were targeted and effective, important words, key concepts, and skills were extracted directly from the competencies and objectives. These essential ideas became the basis for developing the content.

Table 2 lists the topics/lessons of the contextualized learning materials for the second quarter of English 8.

Table 2

Titles and Essential Content Developed of Contextualized Learning Materials for English 8

Module	Learning Competency	Module’s Title	Essential Content Developed
Module 1	Explain visual-verbal relationships illustrated in tables, graphs, and	Visual Verbal Relationships	Understanding visual aids like graphs, charts, maps; how to relate them to texts

Module	Learning Competency	Module's Title	Essential Content Developed
	information maps found in expository texts		
Module 2	Use opinion-marking signals to share ideas	Opinion-marking Signals	Recognizing opinion-marking signals, distinguishing facts from opinions
Module 3	Compare and contrast the presentation of the same topic in different multimodal texts	Compare and Contrast Same Topic in Different Multimodal Texts	Comparing different text formats presenting the same topic
Module 4	Compare and contrast own opinions with those presented in familiar texts	Compare and Contrast Own Opinions with those Presented in Familiar Texts	Stating one's own views and comparing them to others' ideas presented in texts
Module 5	Recognize positive and negative messages conveyed in a text	Recognizing Positive and Negative Messages	Identifying language that signals positive or negative tone

Through the careful breakdown of the learning competencies and specified learning objectives, the researcher was able to organize content that directly addressed the observed gaps in students' mastery levels. This way ensured that learning content were relevant, achievable, and appropriate to students' needs, as observed in the data analysis of the previous year's mastery level of the lesson for each objective.

Correspondingly, each piece of content was examined, and any extraneous or unrelated content was eliminated to emphasize the main ideas and concepts directly related to the learning competencies. The contextualized learning materials reflect the most crucial elements of what must be taught in each lesson, as reflected in the MELCs. The researcher also utilized frameworks such as Bloom's taxonomy to ensure that the selected content covered a range of cognitive complexity levels, from fundamental understanding to higher-order thinking abilities, including analysis, evaluation, and creation. The more complex subjects were divided into smaller, more manageable, and easier-to-understand tasks. Furthermore, the information was presented in a sequential manner, which facilitates understanding and retention. The ideas, concepts, and points conveyed are stated clearly, and many topics are provided carefully and accurately, accompanied by a range of additional exercises.

Furthermore, the learning material's contents were enhanced by adding visual aids, including charts, graphs, and pictures. Students can better understand challenging ideas when they see them presented visually in this lesson. Most importantly, the researcher also provided examples and applications from everyday situations to demonstrate the material's value and relevance in real-world contexts. This aids students in making the connection between theoretical ideas and practical situations.

This vital characteristic of learning material is supported by the study of Capuyan (2021), which emphasizes that the contextualized teaching and learning approach, which incorporates real-life scenarios and activities, enhances students' critical thinking, problem-solving, and creative capabilities. This approach ties theoretical knowledge to practical applications, making learning more meaningful and relevant to students' lives.

Lastly, the researcher reviewed and improved the learning materials based on the validators' suggestions. The content was modified to enhance relevance, clarity, and usefulness in achieving the learning objectives.

Language

To ensure that the language used in the contextualized learning materials was appropriate for Grade 8 students, the researcher conducted a data analysis using results from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). This assessment provided valuable insights into the students' reading levels, common reading difficulties, and comprehension abilities. Under the reading level category, 18 students (60%) were identified at the instructional level, 10 (33%) at the independent level, and two (7%) at the frustration level. This variation implies that the materials should use simplified sentence structures and avoid complex clause combinations, aiming for a maximum readability level equivalent to Grade 7 to accommodate all learners. For common oral reading errors, students often substituted multisyllabic or unfamiliar words and mispronounced words with silent letters (e.g., "doubt," "island"), indicating that selected vocabulary should be high-frequency, age-appropriate, and phonically regular while avoiding rare or jargon-filled terms. In comprehension questions, students performed best with literal questions but struggled with inferential and evaluative ones. This suggests that instructions and discussions in the materials should use clear, direct language, and abstract ideas must be paired with concrete examples or visual aids for better understanding. For fluency and expression, most students read aloud without natural intonation or proper pauses, which means texts should be structured with punctuation cues and sentence lengths that support natural rhythm. Lastly, in cultural relevance and familiarity, students understood better the content rooted in local contexts (e.g., family, barangay events) than foreign topics. Therefore, the materials included localized names, places, and situations to help students relate more easily and promote better comprehension. These findings served as a basis for selecting language that is age-appropriate, culturally relevant, and suited to the learners' instructional needs.

When choosing the correct language to develop the learning material, the researcher considered the target audience, topic content, and context. Initially, the researcher assessed the linguistics skills, cultural influences, and demographics of the Grade 8 students to determine which language they were most comfortable with. Likewise, localization was considered, modifying the content linguistically and culturally to make it more relevant and accessible to the students.

Based on these considerations, the researcher ensured that the terminology and instructions were appropriate for the learners' age and educational background by using language easily understood by the students and avoiding excessively technical or academic vocabulary. The clear, concise, and simple presentation of the instructions enhances the learners' understanding of the content of the learning material.

Additionally, the language used promotes learning objectives. The researcher ensured that the selected language successfully communicates and engages learners

using precise and unambiguous instructions. Additionally, the teachings are delivered in grammatically correct sentences and paragraphs.

Ultimately, the researcher ensured that the terminology, style, and language were consistent throughout the learning material to prevent misunderstandings and improve student retention. Based on the validators' feedback, the language was found to relate to learners and effectively conveyed the content.

Assessment

The learning competencies, specified objectives, content, and the students' needs were carefully considered during the creation of the module's assessment and evaluation tasks, which helped ensure that the assessment tasks were relevant and engaging for them.

To ensure the assessment types used in the contextualized learning materials were both effective and engaging, the researcher conducted a data analysis of the quizzes administered during the second quarter of the previous school year in English 8. The study involved 30 Grade 8 students and aimed to identify which assessment formats best supported learning outcomes and sustained student interest.

The highest-performing and most engaging activities were matching types, word puzzles, and self-assessment surveys, all of which scored above 85% and effectively engaged more than 24 students. Assessments involving writing (sentence construction and interpreting) showed moderate scores but were intellectually beneficial in building foundational skills. Combination formats, such as multiple-choice, paragraph-making, and drawing opinions, helped scaffold complex skills in a way that supported learners across different ability levels. Student engagement observations during assessments revealed that tasks combining visuals, structure, and creativity resulted in higher focus, participation, and enjoyment.

Furthermore, the activities were designed to measure the desired learning results. The researcher also ensured that each test question was linked to a specific learning objective. Contextualized learning materials also facilitated self-evaluation. Additionally, the researcher provided clear directions and explained why these tests and evaluation activities were necessary, including details about the evaluation criteria and any useful tools or resources.

The researcher also guaranteed that the tests and evaluations measured higher-order thinking skills, which helps students understand and remember what they have learned. The test questions were carefully written to ensure that students could understand them. Moreover, the response to one inquiry serves as a guide for another, enhancing comprehension by establishing connections between concepts. This interconnected approach helps learners build deeper comprehension, recognize relationships between ideas, and improve critical thinking skills.

The learning materials were contextualized by integrating situations students frequently encounter daily. This approach allows learners to relate the content to their experiences, making learning more meaningful and engaging. Similarly, Perin (2011) explored the impact of contextualized instruction on student learning. The study found that integrating real-life scenarios into assessments facilitated better understanding and retention of information, as students could relate theoretical concepts to practical applications.

The researcher modified and enhanced the assessment based on the feedback from the validators regarding the developed contextualized learning materials.

Layout and Packaging

The researcher began the data analysis by reviewing DepEd's RM No. 91 s. 2020 guidelines, which outlined design standards such as the recommended color palettes (light blue cover, white interior) and the required dimensions for modules (A4, bond paper). To ensure the design resonated with the target audience, the researcher also surveyed the Grade 8 students. Through this, it was discovered that students had a strong preference for bright, relatable imagery, including classroom scenes and pictures of students actively engaged in studying.

The layout and packaging were carefully considered to incorporate contrast, balance, emphasis, proportion, rhythm, pattern, white space, variety, and unity, resulting in a well-structured layout that looked visually appealing. This included the cover page of the module that was made. The contextualized learning materials featured a vibrant cover with books in the background to represent information. For the cover design, Canva application was utilized, showing pictures of students answering the module, a teacher in the classroom, and a student reading a book. This was done to ensure that the cover aligned with the purpose of the module and its intended audience.

In RM No. 91 S. 2020— Elements of a Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) Learning Module, the module's color scheme is based on the guidelines specifying that light blue is an appropriate color. The guidelines stipulated that the background color of other pages must be white to have a clean and professional appearance.

The color themes and other standardized design elements show the DepEd commitment to providing students nationwide with concise and uniform learning materials. Each part of the contextualized learning materials is exhibited by a picture that tells the learners what to do or what skills they must work on. These design decisions aimed to make the layout, cover page, and packaging stand out. The researcher also incorporated critical visual elements that complemented the theme of the content, effectively maintaining students' attention. The researcher identified the optimal combination by experimenting with various layouts and arrangements of the images, ensuring that the cover page looked both engaging and professional. The finished design was printed on bond paper in A4 size, with a total of 92 sheets in all the learning materials.

Figure 5 shows the cover page of the Contextualized Learning Materials for English 8.

Figure 5

Cover page of the Contextualized Learning Materials for English 8

Research Question 2. Level of Validity of the Contextualized Learning Materials for English 8

Using the survey checklist adapted from Salazar (2018), the validators evaluated the contextualized learning materials for English 8 regarding the four essential elements: learning objectives, content, language, and assessment. The validators, composed of English Supervisors, Master Teachers, and Teachers, rated each indicator of the components of the learning materials.

Table 3 presents validators' ratings on the objectives of contextualized learning materials for English 8.

Table 3*Rating on the Learning Objectives of the Contextualized Learning Materials for English 8*

Characteristics of the objectives of the module	Frequency of responses					Mean	SD	VI	D
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. A specific objective accompanies each lesson in the module.	16	2	0	0	0	4.89	0.323	VMV	E
2. The words used in the objective are clear and easily understood.	12	6	0	0	0	4.67	0.485	VMV	E
3. The specific objectives are realistic.	12	6	0	0	0	4.67	0.485	VMV	E
4. The objectives are measurable.	13	5	0	0	0	4.72	0.461	VMV	E
5. The specific objectives are attainable within specified time limit.	8	10	0	0	0	4.44	0.511	VMV	E
Composite Mean						4.68	0.470	VMV	E

Legend:

<i>Mean Interval</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation (VI)</i>	<i>Description (D)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (SD)</i>
4.20 – 5.00	Very Much Valid (VMV)	Excellent (E)	
3.40 – 4.19	Much Valid (MuV)	Very Satisfactory (VS)	
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Valid (MV)	Satisfactory (S)	
1.80 – 2.59	Less Valid (LV)	Fair (F)	
1.00 – 1.79	Not Valid (NV)	Poor (P)	

The majority of the respondents rated it “very much valid” across all indicators. This is supported by an overall mean score of 4.68. Most of the validators assigned a score of “5” as the highest, noting that the learning goals were attainable within the given timeframe, practical, measurable, clear, and simple to understand. This means that the learning goals are well-organized and straightforward, helping students achieve their objectives. Overall, the findings indicate that the resources align with necessary teaching standards.

Moss and Brookhart (2019) explained that clear learning objectives help students understand what they need to learn, thereby improving their engagement and comprehension while also guiding teachers in delivering focused lessons. This directly aligns with the researcher's findings, which show that the objectives of the contextualized learning materials significantly contributed to high student involvement. The clarity of the objectives helped students understand what was expected of them, keeping them actively engaged in the learning process. At the same time, it served as an effective guide for teachers in planning and delivering lessons more efficiently and purposefully.

Table 4 shows the validators' ratings of the content of the contextualized learning materials.

Table 4*Rating on the Content of the Contextualized Learning Materials for English 8*

Characteristics of the content of the module	Frequency of responses					Mean	SD	VI	D
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. Each lesson reflects the most important aspects of what is being taught.	12	5	1	0	0	4.61	0.608	VMV	E
2. The lessons are presented at a pace that allows for reflection and review.	10	7	1	0	0	4.50	0.618	VMV	E
3. There is adequate provision for supplementary activities/exercises.	10	8	0	0	0	4.56	0.511	VMV	E
4. The content leads to the attainment of the objectives.	13	4	0	1	0	4.61	0.778	VMV	E
5. There is adequate presentation/discussion of content.	12	5	1	0	0	4.61	0.608	VMV	E
6. The information about the different topics is accurate and precise.	11	7	0	0	0	4.61	0.502	VMV	E
7. There is a variety of supplementary activities.	13	5	0	0	0	4.72	0.461	VMV	E
8. The ideas, concepts, and points presented are well-expressed.	12	5	1	0	0	4.61	0.608	VMV	E
9. The examples presented are current, accurate, and defensible.	13	4	1	0	0	4.67	0.594	VMV	E
10. The lessons are aligned with the curriculum.	13	4	1	0	0	4.67	0.594	VMV	E
Composite Mean						4.62	0.582	VMV	E

*Legend:***Mean Interval**

4.20 – 5.00

3.40 – 4.19

2.60 – 3.39

1.80 – 2.59

1.00 – 1.79

Verbal Interpretation (VI)

Very Much Valid (VMV)

Much Valid (MuV)

Moderately Valid (MV)

Less Valid (LV)

Not Valid (NV)

Description (D)

Excellent (E)

Very Satisfactory (VS)

Satisfactory (S)

Fair (F)

Poor (P)

Standard Deviation (SD)

The content of the materials was also rated “very much valid” (VMV), with an average score of 4.62. This high rating means the lessons cover the most essential topics in English 8 for the second quarter. Furthermore, they align with the curriculum and include sufficient activities to help students practice what they have learned. The lessons are structured at a good pace, allowing students to reflect on and review the topics. The examples and discussions are also accurate and relevant, making the content more meaningful to students.

The module enhances learning experiences by incorporating visual aids like diagrams, charts, and illustrations, which help clarify complex concepts and improve comprehension. Real-life examples and applications are included to demonstrate the relevance of the content, ensuring learners can effectively apply their knowledge in practical situations.

A study by Varthana (2021) found that visual aids such as charts, diagrams, and illustrations effectively enhance student comprehension and retention. These tools help

simplify complex concepts, making them more accessible and engaging for learners. This supports the researcher's findings, as the incorporation of illustrations in the contextualized learning materials was recognized as an effective strategy that improved students' learning and comprehension.

The researcher's findings explain that students are more engaged and better able to understand lessons when they are attracted to and supported by visual illustrations. This agrees with the result of the study of Yongco and Del Valle (2022), which highlights the importance of using illustrations to facilitate easier learning.

Table 5 shows the ratings of the validators for the language used in the contextualized learning materials.

Table 5

Rating on the Language Used in the Contextualized Learning Materials

Characteristics of language used	Frequency of responses					Mean	SD	VI	D
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. The words used in the module are correctly used.	12	6	0	0	0	4.67	0.485	VMV	E
2. The module is accompanied by clear and specific directions for their use.	14	4	0	0	0	4.78	0.428	VMV	E
3. The vocabulary used suits the reading and understanding level of students to whom the modules are intended.	9	7	2	0	0	4.39	0.698	VMV	E
4. Instructions to the students are clear, unambiguous, and easy to follow.	10	8	0	0	0	4.56	0.511	VMV	E
5. The lessons are presented in paragraphs.	11	7	0	0	0	4.61	0.502	VMV	E
	Composite Mean					4.60	0.536	VMV	E

Legend:

<i>Mean Interval</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation (VI)</i>	<i>Description (D)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (SD)</i>
4.20 – 5.00	Very Much Valid (VMV)	Excellent (E)	
3.40 – 4.19	Much Valid (MuV)	Very Satisfactory (VS)	
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Valid (MV)	Satisfactory (S)	
1.80 – 2.59	Less Valid (LV)	Fair (F)	
1.00 – 1.79	Not Valid (NV)	Poor (P)	

It revealed that the language used in the texts is “very much valid,” with an overall mean of 4.60. This means that the words used are appropriate to the students' reading level and that there are clear instructions on how to use them. The language used in the lesson is accessible, meaning the words are common and easy for learners to understand. There are no complicated technical words that might be hard to understand.

Similarly, the reading level is ideal for the age and educational level of the readers, who are Grade 8 students. The words are suitable for their reading and understanding levels, making things clear. Students can do their work correctly because the instructions are precise, exact, and easy to follow. This shows that the language used in the learning material is suitable for the student's level.

Yongco and Del Valle (2022) found that instructional modules should utilize clear and engaging language to enhance students' understanding. The use of simple words and easy-to-follow instructions facilitates learning and makes it more effective.

Table 6 presents the ratings of the assessment activities in the contextualized learning materials for English 8.

Table 6

Rating on the Assessment of the Contextualized Learning Materials for English 8

Characteristics of Assessment and Evaluation Activities	Frequency of responses					Mean	SD	VI	D
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. The module has a provision for self-assessment.	11	6	1	0	0	4.56	0.616	VMV	E
2. The items help increase understanding and retention of the content.	13	3	2	0	0	4.61	0.698	VMV	E
3. The items focus on important objectives and content of the lessons.	14	2	2	0	0	4.67	0.686	VMV	E
4. The items in the evaluation are congruent to the specific objectives.	13	4	1	0	0	4.67	0.594	VMV	E
5. Some items measure higher thinking skills.	12	4	2	0	0	4.56	0.705	VMV	E
6. The items are grammatically correct.	13	4	1	0	0	4.67	0.594	VMV	E
7. The items are arranged from easy to difficult.	10	6	2	0	0	4.44	0.705	VMV	E
8. The test items are written at a level that students can understand.	10	6	2	0	0	4.44	0.705	VMV	E
9. The answer to one item furnishes or gives clue to the answer to another item.	8	8	2	0	0	4.33	0.686	VMV	E
10. The items cover the important competencies to be developed.	13	4	1	0	0	4.67	0.594	VMV	E
Composite Mean						4.56	.653	VMV	E

Legend:

<i>Mean Interval</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation (VI)</i>	<i>Description (D)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (SD)</i>
4.20 – 5.00	Very Much Valid (VMV)	Excellent (E)	
3.40 – 4.19	Much Valid (MuV)	Very Satisfactory (VS)	
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Valid (MV)	Satisfactory (S)	
1.80 – 2.59	Less Valid (LV)	Fair (F)	
1.00 – 1.79	Not Valid (NV)	Poor (P)	

The assessment activities in the contextualized materials got a “very much valid” (VMV) rating, with an average score of 4.56, suggesting that the activities are well-organized and closely related to the lesson objectives. The test questions were well-written, logically ordered from easy to hard, and designed to encourage critical thinking. Additionally, self-assessment tasks were included to help students evaluate their learning progress. The test items also facilitate learning and retention, measure higher-order thinking skills, and ensure correct grammar. Grade 8 students, even those with special

needs, can do the assessment tasks. However, some questions on the test give students hints about how to answer other questions. The test questions were carefully written at a level suitable for students and covered the essential skills they need to learn.

Campbell (2021) highlighted that assessments designed to measure higher-order thinking skills and provide clear instructions enhance understanding and retention, facilitating learning by making complex concepts more accessible and promoting critical thinking. This relates to the researcher's study, as the contextualized learning materials were developed with clear assessment instructions and activities that aimed to develop students' critical thinking skills. These assessments supported deeper understanding and helped students engage meaningfully with the content.

Table 7 summarizes the validation results for the developed contextualized learning materials for English 8.

Table 7

Summary Result of Rating on the Validation of the Developed Contextualized Learning Materials

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Description
1. Objectives of the module	4.68	0.470	Very Much Valid	Excellent
2. Content of the module	4.62	0.582	Very Much Valid	Excellent
3. Language used	4.60	0.536	Very Much Valid	Excellent
4. Assessment and Evaluation Activities	4.56	.653	Very Much Valid	Excellent
Overall Mean	4.62	.560	Very Much Valid	Excellent

Legend:

<i>Mean Interval</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (SD)</i>
4.20 – 5.00	Very Much Valid	Excellent	
3.40 – 4.19	Much Valid	Very Satisfactory	
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Valid	Satisfactory	
1.80 – 2.59	Less Valid	Fair	
1.00 – 1.79	Not Valid	Poor	

Table 7 shows that the contextualized learning materials are “very much valid”. This was validated by the supervisors, master teachers, and English teachers from secondary schools in the Torrijos District.

Statistics show that, across all indicators, the validity is very much supported, with an overall mean of 4.62, indicating that the module is highly valid. However, the validators' comments and suggestions should be considered to improve contextualized learning materials.

Research Question 3. Comments, Feedback, and Suggestions of the Validators to Help Enhance the Developed Contextualized Learning Materials in English 8

The validators gave positive feedback on the developed contextualized learning materials, emphasizing their support for teachers and students. They stated that the learning materials help teachers teach by providing them with beneficial ways and strategies that enable teachers and students to learn effectively. The learning materials were also commended for being well-organized, covering the target skills, and aligning with the learning competencies. Also, the learning materials have specific objectives that can be reached, ensuring the lessons are practical. They noted that the materials look good, with pictures, colors, and writing that is clear and bright, making it easy for students to understand what they are reading. Furthermore, activities and tasks are significant to English 8 skills and learning competencies, making the lessons valuable and relevant for the students.

The validators who reviewed the learning materials added that the tasks and examples were well-contextualized, making the lessons easier to understand. The localized and relevant material makes students more interested in their learning.

The study by Givera (2023) demonstrated that contextualized and localized English learning materials, validated for content accuracy and relevance, significantly improved students' performance and engagement, making lessons more straightforward to understand and relatable. The learning materials were also praised for being easy to understand because they are written in simple language appropriate for Grade 8 students. Validators also appreciated how challenging these learning materials were, as they knew they would help teachers in their lessons.

To improve the usefulness of the learning materials, the validators suggested paying attention to the content's structure and quality by ensuring that the subject-verb order and sentence usage are consistently maintained. They proposed eliminating extraneous words and reducing unnecessary lectures and discussions that do not contribute to student learning. Certain parts need to be more precise and focused, and specific explanations could be made longer to make them more understandable. Regarding the curriculum and how lessons are taught, validators stated that learning outcomes and assessments should be firmly connected.

Denoyelles (2021) emphasized the importance of aligning module objectives with evaluations to improve student understanding, engagement, and academic performance by ensuring that assessments accurately reflect the intended learning outcomes. This is reflected in the researcher's study, where the contextualized learning materials were carefully designed to ensure alignment between the learning objectives and the assessments. This alignment helped reinforce students' understanding and engagement, supporting their progress toward the intended learning goals.

The validators' inputs were considered to enhance the learning materials and make them more effective for Grade 8 learners. They were categorized into specific

themes to ensure that the feedback was organized. Considering the validators' thoughts and ideas, the contextualized learning materials were refined to support teachers and students better, making the learning process more effective and meaningful.

Table 8 summarizes the validators' comments and feedback on enhancing the developed contextualized learning materials in English 8.

Table 8

Coding and Thematic Analysis of Validators' Feedback

Theme	Validators' Feedback
Support for Teachers and Learners	The learning materials will assist teachers in teaching. The modules offer helpful teaching techniques and strategies. The modules benefit both teachers and students in the learning process.
Engagement and Visual Appeal	The materials are visually appealing, with readable text and bright colors. Illustrations make the content easier to understand for students.
Curriculum Alignment and Competency Coverage	The learning materials are aligned with the curriculum and cover the English 8 competencies.
Contextualization	Activities and examples are tailored to make the lesson more straightforward to understand. The activities and examples are localized, making them more engaging for students. The modules are well-developed and relevant to students.
Achievement of Learning Outcomes	The learning materials include clear, achievable outcomes. The materials are engaging and suited to the student's level of understanding. The assessments match the learning objectives.
Simplicity and Accessibility	The materials use simple language that is accessible to Grade 8 learners. The modules are simplified and easy to understand, supporting the learning process.

Support for Teachers and Learners

The supervisor-validator thanked the researcher for her interest and effort in helping English 8 teachers. Likewise, two master teachers and one teacher validator wrote that the learning materials would greatly help Grade 8 teachers and learners in the teaching and learning process. Moreover, another teacher-validator highlighted that the modules incorporate effective techniques and strategies that help impart knowledge to students more efficiently.

Engagement and Visual Appeal

One teacher-validator noted that the pictures in the modules effectively get students' attention and encourage them to do the tasks and follow the lessons. Another pointed out that illustrations help the learners understand the lesson's content. One teacher-validator of the learning materials added that the pictures are updated, the font size is easy to read, and the materials are colorful. Adding bright and well-designed elements makes students even more interested and involved in the learning process.

Curriculum Alignment and Competency Coverage

One master teacher-validator and three teacherValidators confirmed that the learning materials are aligned with the curriculum. They stated that the lessons, objectives, and activities effectively cover the target competencies outlined in the English 8 Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). This alignment ensures that students learn the essential skills and information appropriate for their grade level as prescribed by the DepEd. With this alignment, the lessons become beneficial and valuable learning tools for effective instruction.

Achievement of Learning Outcomes

As noted by one teacher-validator, the contextualized learning materials have achievable, specific, and clear goals. Three teacherValidators believe that the content is interesting, simple to understand, and suitable for learners' current level of knowledge. Another teacher-validator also emphasized how well the assessments align with the learning objectives, ensuring that students can understand the lessons. Additionally, the materials were praised for encouraging student engagement, with the activities being both stimulating and relevant to the learners' everyday experiences. This has fostered a deeper connection to the content, ensuring that the learning outcomes are not only met but also retained effectively. The structure of the lessons was also acknowledged for its logical flow, which enables students to progressively build their knowledge and skills, leading to greater achievement of the set learning objectives.

Simplicity and Accessibility

One teacher-validator noted that the contextualized learning resources utilize simple language that students in Grade 8 can understand. According to a second teacher-validator, students can follow the lectures more easily because the learning materials are easy to comprehend. The contextualized learning materials are comprehensible and simplified, allowing students to grasp the content quickly and efficiently. This accessibility of the learning materials enhances the teaching-learning process by streamlining the content and details for learners to comprehend and access learning.

One teacher-validator suggested providing printed copies of the learning materials to Grade 8 students so that they could easily access them. Students will be more interested in the lessons if the materials are provided in print. These learning materials

can also facilitate self-paced learning, which allows students to study at their own pace. Ensuring all students can access the materials will help them learn more effectively and understand the lessons easier.

Contextualization

According to four teacher-validators, the activities and examples in the modules are contextualized, making the lessons more straightforward for students to understand. They emphasized how learning becomes more engaging and relatable for students when the content is localized. Additionally, three other teacher-validators who validated the contextualized learning resources stated they were well-developed and relevant to the learners. The activities were also created to fit the students' abilities and understanding levels to guarantee they would learn well from the contextualized learning materials.

Figure 6 illustrates the researcher's sample revision to enhance the content's contextualization and relevance to students' learning experiences.

Figure 6

Revisions made for Contextualization

Here are examples of opinions using opinion-markings signals.

Source: <https://www.traveloka.com/en-ph/explore/destination/vacation-in-boracay-philippines-a-complete-guide-to-the-tourist-hotspot-acc/257164>

1. For me, Boracay is the best tourist destination in the Philippines.
2. Tourists love to watch the radiant sunset in the picturesque Boracay Beach.
3. I think Boracay Island attracts many tourists during summer, a perfect time for beach activities, water sports, and sunbathing.

Source: <https://dyosathemomma.com/how-to-make-your-childs-first-birthday-party-enjoyable-for-everyone/>

1. I am sure that the children enjoy the birthday party.
2. I guess, they are celebrating the first birthday of their cousin.
3. I feel that the kids are excited for the games and prizes that await them.

Here are examples of opinions using opinion-markings signals.

Photo source: *Morion Travel and Tours Facebook post, February 15, 2025.*

1. In my opinion, Torrijos White Beach is the best tourist destination in the Philippines.
2. I believe that tourists are captivated by the radiant sunset at Torrijos White Beach.
3. I think summer is the perfect season to enjoy sunbathing in Torrijos White Beach.

1. I love the biko in Marinduque because it tastes sweet and is always served during special occasions.
2. I'm sure many people enjoy eating biko, especially during birthdays and town fiestas.
3. I feel that biko is a special food that brings families together in Marinduque.

The researcher revised the contextualized learning materials for English 8 by replacing generic and distant content with images and examples that are more familiar to the students. Originally, the lesson used a picture of Boracay Beach, a well-known but distant location that some students may not have experienced personally. However, upon the validator's suggestion, the researcher replaced it with a photo of Poctoy White Beach Resort, a well-known local destination in the students' area, to increase relevance and engagement. Similarly, a birthday party image sourced from the internet was changed to a picture of *biko*, a traditional Filipino delicacy often served during local celebrations, which students are more likely to recognize from personal experience. Along with these visual changes, the researcher also revised the opinion-marking sentences to match the new images and better reflect the learners' cultural and real-life context. These adjustments were made to ensure that the materials would be more meaningful, relatable, and effective for Grade 8 learners.

Table 9 shows the results of the coding and thematic analysis based on the validators' suggestions. It summarizes the common ideas and comments they gave to help improve the contextualized learning materials.

Table 9*Coding and Thematic Analysis of Validators' Suggestions*

Theme	Validators' Suggestions
Content Quality and Structure	Focus on consistency, ensuring that the subject, verb, and tense align correctly in some of the sentences in the learning materials. Reduce the number of lectures and eliminate discussions that do not contribute to achieving the objectives. Reduce any extraneous words. Make some sections clear and focused. Additionally, the explanations could be expanded to provide more detailed information and clarity
Curriculum and Instructional Design	Ensure the alignment of the learning objectives and assessments. I recommend conducting a pilot test with a small group of learners. Some words should be changed to match the student's level of understanding.
Accessibility and Inclusivity Citation Formatting	Ensure materials are accessible to all learners. Cite the online sources properly.

Content Quality and Structure

The supervisor and some teacher-validators emphasized the importance of consistency, correct grammar, proper punctuation, and appropriate capitalization in the development of the learning materials, particularly in aligning subjects, verbs, and tenses within sentences. These elements are essential in ensuring that students can clearly understand the content without confusion. In response, the researcher made several key revisions to improve clarity and correctness, such as editing sentences for grammatical accuracy, adjusting punctuation marks for proper pauses and meaning, and standardizing capitalization for uniformity and readability. These improvements aimed to enhance the overall quality of the learning materials and support better student learning.

Figure 7

Revisions made for Content Quality and Structure (a)

- Do you think these ways of presenting topic affect people feelings and decision-making?
- For you, is it alright to present one topic in different ways? Why?

The topic presented in the three sources of information is all about promoting Philippines supported by its taglines, "It's more fun in the Philippines". The information is presented in three different ways: YouTube, Facebook, and Poster. Nevertheless, they share the same topic. In the video, topic is presented through displaying moving images and video clips because of the transitions applied in editing the video, with the accompany of lively music. On the other

- Do you think these ways of presenting the topic affect people's feelings and decision-making?
- For you, is it alright to present one topic in different ways? Why?

The topic presented in the three sources of information is all about promoting Philippines supported by its tagline, "It's more fun in the Philippines". The information is presented in three different ways: YouTube, Facebook, and Poster. Nevertheless, they share the same topic. In the video, topic is presented through displaying moving images and video clips because of the transitions applied in editing the video, with the accompaniment of lively music. On the

For example, the word "topic" was changed to "the topic" to include the appropriate determiner; "people" was corrected to "people's" to show proper possessive form; and the phrase "with the accompany of music" was revised to "with the accompaniment of music" to use the correct noun form.

Figure 8

Revisions made for Content Quality and Structure (b)

- | | | |
|--|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Learning Competency: Compare and contrast own opinions with those presented in familiar texts
▪ Learning Objectives:
After going through this module, you are expected to:<ul style="list-style-type: none">• use compare and contrast transition signals in giving opinions;• compare and contrast the details in the text using a venn diagram; and• formulate opinions on familiar text using compare and contrast transition signals. | | <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Learning Competency: compare and contrast own opinions with those presented in familiar texts
▪ Learning Objectives:
After going through this module, you are expected to:<ul style="list-style-type: none">• use compare and contrast transition signals in giving opinions• compare and contrast the details in the text using a venn diagram• write opinions on familiar text using compare and contrast transition signals |
|--|---|---|

In this example of writing learning objectives, the researcher ensured proper capitalization by beginning the learning competency with a capital letter. Correct punctuation was also observed, particularly the use of semicolons to separate each objective in the list, which facilitated better readability and organization. A period was correctly placed at the end of the final sentence to indicate completion. Additionally, the connector "and" was properly used before the last item to show that it is part of a series. These revisions reflect the researcher's careful attention to grammar, punctuation, and structure, resulting in clear and professionally written learning objectives.

Figure 9

Revisions made for Content Quality and Structure (c)

In this part, the verb “was declared” was changed to “declared” in the sentence. The researcher made this change to make the sentence clearer and to use the correct verb tense. Since the subject “a municipal ordinance” is the one doing the action, it is better to use the simple past tense “declared” instead of the passive form “was declared.” This helps students understand the sentence more easily and shows good grammar, which is important when creating learning materials.

In addition, one master teacher-validator suggested reducing the number of lectures and eliminating discussions that do not contribute to achieving the main objectives. Two teacher-validators suggested that reducing unnecessary words would make the text more transparent and focused. However, explanations should be detailed to provide a deeper understanding and clarity. The content should be direct and to the point to help students focus on the most important information that must be learned, thereby avoiding confusion or distraction from irrelevant details. This way, learners can easily identify and absorb the key concepts, which supports better comprehension and retention.

Here is an example of a revision made by the researcher in response to the validator's input.

Figure 10

Revisions made for Content Quality and Structure (d)

What Is It?

MULTIMODAL TEXT refers to any form of communication that uses more than one mode or method of communication to convey meaning. It comes from the Latin word “multi” which means “many” and “modus,” meaning “method or manner”.

Modes can include a combination of written language, images, sounds, gestures, and other forms of communication. Here are the key modes involved in multimodal texts:

1. Linguistic Mode- this mode involves the use of words, either spoken or written, to convey meaning. Conversations, speeches, audio recordings, and dialogues in videos are examples of spoken language while essays, emails, websites, captions, and subtitles, are some of the examples of written text.
2. Visual Mode – this mode includes the use of images, colors, layouts, and other visual elements to represent meaning. This is powerful especially for quickly capturing attention and conveying emotions or complex ideas without relying solely on words.

3. Aural Mode – this mode refers to the use of sound, music, and tone to create meaning. This is important in multimedia forms like videos, podcasts, and live presentations, adding an emotional and dynamic layer to communication.

4. Gestural Mode – this mode involves movement, body language, and facial expressions to communicate meaning. It includes smiles, hand movements, head nods, and other physical cues that emphasize and clarify spoken words.

5. Spatial Mode – this refers to how elements are arranged in physical or digital space to guide the audience's interaction and interpretation. This includes the layout of the text and images, proximity and alignment, and use of space, that can influence meaning or usability. Spatial mode is particularly important in digital media, advertising, web design, and architecture, where the placement of elements directly affects how information is processed by the audience.

In education, the combination of modes is particularly beneficial for students as it caters to different styles, making information more accessible and engaging, ultimately enhancing comprehension and retention.

Multimodal texts can be in print, digital, and live forms.

A. PRINT or PAPER-BASED MULTIMODAL TEXTS

- are physical documents that combine modes of communication on printed media. These often rely on the tactile experience and visual arrangement to enhance understanding and engagement.

1. Books and Magazine – incorporating images, charts, and layout design alongside written articles that work together to engage the reader.

What Is It?

MULTIMODAL TEXT refers to any form of communication that uses more than one mode or method of communication to convey meaning. It comes from the Latin word “multi” which means “many” and “modus,” meaning “method or manner”.

Modes can include a combination of written language, images, sounds, gestures, and other forms of communication.

In education, the combination of modes is particularly beneficial for students as it caters to different styles, making information more accessible and engaging, ultimately enhancing comprehension and retention.

Multimodal texts can be in print, digital, and live forms.

A. PRINT or PAPER-BASED MULTIMODAL TEXTS

- are physical documents that combine modes of communication on printed media. These often rely on the tactile experience and visual arrangement to enhance understanding and engagement.

1. Books and Magazine – incorporating images, charts, and layout design alongside written articles that work together to engage the reader.

<https://www.readingandwritinghaven.com/best-books-for-english-teachers-professional-development>

2. Posters – utilize visual elements such as images and graphics alongside minimal text to communicate messages effectively, often used in educational or promotional purposes.

<https://web.nlp.gov.ph/malipayang-ituson-ng-wikang-pambansa-2024/>

<https://www.arpal.com/flashilicommunicate/261757-7>

In this example, the researcher revised the original content by removing the lengthy explanation of each mode of communication—linguistic, visual, aural, gestural, and spatial—which, although informative, made the lesson too detailed and diverted focus from the main objective. Following the validator’s suggestion to be more direct and focused, the researcher kept only the definition of multimodal text and emphasized its application in education, such as how combining different modes helps students learn better by catering to various learning styles. After this brief explanation, the revised content now directly introduces the main topic: the types of multimodal texts—print, digital, and live—which keeps the discussion clear and aligned with the learning goal. This revision helps students focus on what they need to learn without being overwhelmed by too much background information.

To conclude, these changes have improved the learning materials, making them more effective for teaching and learning. Consequently, the contextualized learning materials are now organized, concise, and valuable for both students and teachers.

Curriculum and Instructional Design

A master teacher-validator suggested that the learning objectives should match the learning assessments to ensure alignment between what is taught and what is evaluated. This means that the skills or knowledge stated in the objectives must be reflected in the assessment tasks. By aligning the objectives and assessments, students are better guided on what they are expected to learn, and teachers can accurately measure if those objectives have been achieved. This alignment also helps maintain the focus of the lesson and supports effective teaching and learning.

Figure 11

Revisions made for Curriculum and Instructional Design (a)

Create a slogan on the essence of friendship using words and expressions that signal positive message. Use the criteria below: Express the essence of friendship by creating a slogan that uses words and expressions that signal positive message. Use the criteria below:

Criteria	Points
Relevance to the theme	20
Message	20
Impact (neatness, presentation, color harmony)	10
Total	50

Criteria	Points
Relevance to the theme	20
Message	20
Impact (neatness, presentation, color harmony)	10
Total	50

In this example, the learning objective is to *"Express the essence of friendship in writing a slogan using words and expressions that signal a positive message."* However, in the original version, the learning task was stated as *"Create a slogan on the essence of friendship using words and expressions that signal positive message,"* which did not fully reflect the structure and intent of the objective. To address this, the researcher revised the task to *"Express the essence of friendship by creating a slogan using words and*

expressions that signal a positive message" to align it with the objective. This revision ensures that the action stated in the objective ("express") is directly mirrored in the task, creating a stronger connection between what the students are expected to learn and how they are expected to demonstrate that learning.

Another suggestion for student teacher-validators was changing certain words to better match their understanding. This modification helped simplify the language, allowing students to grasp the instructions more easily. By using simpler words, the researcher ensured that students could focus on what they needed to learn without getting confused. This change made the learning materials more effective and easier to follow.

Figure 12

Revisions made for Curriculum and Instructional Design (b)

C. Read the following text carefully. Recognize the positive and negative messages in the text by underlining the part that indicates the message.

Text 1. The Pros and Cons of Using Social Media

C. Read the following text carefully. Recognize the positive and negative messages in the text by underlining the part that indicates the message.

Text 1. The Positive and Negative Effects of Using Social Media

In this example, the validator suggested making the title clearer and more precise, so the researcher changed "*The pros and cons of using media*" to "*The positive and negative effects of using social media*." By replacing "pros and cons" with "positive and negative effects," and specifying "social media," the title now uses simpler, more direct language and tells students what to look for in the text. In this example, the validator suggested making the title clearer and more precise, so the researcher changed "The pros and cons of using media" to "The positive and negative effects of using social media." By replacing "pros and cons" with "positive and negative effects," and specifying "social media," the title now uses simpler, more direct language and tells students what to look for in the text. This revision not only improved clarity but also aligned the title more closely with the content of the material, helping students set clear expectations and focus their reading. It also supports better comprehension, especially for learners who may struggle with vague or general terms.

Figure 13

Revisions made for Curriculum and Instructional Design (c)

Importance of Multimodal Texts in Daily Living

Multimodal texts have become integral to daily life as we increasingly engage with technology and media. Learning multimodal texts play a crucial role, particularly in the education of students, especially in the modern digital world.

- Improved Comprehension
- Engagement and Motivation
- Development of Critical Literacy
- Digital Literacy Skills
- Fostering Creativity
- Enhance Understanding
- Cater to Different Learning Styles
- Engage and Capture Attention
- Reflect Real-World Communication

Importance of Multimodal Texts in Daily Living

Multimodal texts are now a big part of daily life because we use technology and media more. Learning these texts is important, especially for students in today's digital world.

- Helps understand better
- Makes learning more interesting
- Improves thinking skills
- Builds digital skills
- Encourages creativity
- Helps explain ideas clearly
- Supports different learning styles
- Grabs attention
- Shows how people communicate in real life

In the original version, the terms used were more academic and formal (e.g., “Enhanced Understanding,” “Development of Critical Literacy,” “Reflect Real-World Communication”). In the revised version, these were replaced with simpler, more student-friendly phrases (e.g., “Helps understand better,” “Improves thinking skills,” “Shows how people communicate in real life”).

This shift in vocabulary ensures that students can more easily grasp the content without being hindered by complex or unfamiliar words. The simplified version maintains the original meaning while making it more accessible, which is essential in educational materials intended for younger audiences or those with varying literacy levels.

To sum up, the researcher selected words that were familiar and appropriate to the students' vocabulary level, ensuring that the content was easily understandable. This adjustment improves the effectiveness of the learning material by allowing students to concentrate on the core concepts rather than struggling with complex language.

Citation Formatting

A master teacher-validator suggested using an appropriate style to cite online sources properly. Correct citations establish credibility and give credit to the writers or authors. This also makes it easy for teachers and students to find references to help them learn more should they need additional ideas. Formatting references correctly makes the learning resources reliable.

Figure 14 shows a sample of the revision made by the researcher.

Figure 14

Revisions made for Citation Formatting

Printed Materials

Gabing, Cris-An T. *English Quarter 2- Module 1: Explaining Visual-Verbal Relationships*. CARAGA Region: Deapartment of Education, First Edition, 2020.

Moreno, Melanie Mae N. *Pivot 4A Learner's Material Quarter 2*. CALABARZON: Department of Education, First Edition 2020.

Podol, Hazel S. *Quarter 2 Module 1: Explain Visual-Verbal Relationships Illustrated in Tables, Graphs, And Information Maps Found in Expository Texts*. Bataan: Department of Education, First Edition, 2020.

Websites

<https://pumble.com/blog/verbal-communication/>

<https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/visual-verbal/250715517>

<https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/visual-verbal/250715517>

<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/8-reasons-positive-impact-technology-human-life-sergii-oliinyk>

<https://www.allrecipes.com/recipe/128699/famous-chicken-adobo/>

Printed Materials

Gabing, C.-A. T. (2020). *English Quarter 2- Module 1: Explaining Visual-Verbal Relationships* (First ed.). Department of Education, CARAGA Region.

Moreno, M. M. N. (2020). *Pivot 4A Learner's Material Quarter 2* (First ed.). Department of Education, CALABARZON.

Podol, H. S. (2020). *Quarter 2 Module 1: Explain Visual-Verbal Relationships Illustrated in Tables, Graphs, and Information Maps Found in Expository Texts* (First ed.). Department of Education, Bataan.

Websites

Pumble. (n.d.). *Verbal communication*. Retrieved July 28, 2024, from <https://pumble.com/blog/verbal-communication/>

Slideshare. (n.d.). *Visual-verbal*. Retrieved July 28, 2024, from <https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/visual-verbal/250715517>

Oliinyk, S. (n.d.). *8 reasons for the positive impact of technology on human life*. LinkedIn. Retrieved August 3, 2024, from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/8-reasons-positive-impact-technology-human-life-sergii-oliinyk>

Allrecipes. (n.d.). *Famous chicken adobo*. Retrieved August 3, 2024, from <https://www.allrecipes.com/recipe/128699/famous-chicken-adobo/>

The revision made by the researcher reflects the validator's suggestion to apply an appropriate citation style, enhancing the academic quality and credibility of the material. In the original list, both printed and online sources lacked proper formatting, consistency, and essential citation elements. Author names were written in full, publication details were inconsistently presented, and web sources lacked titles, retrieval dates, and source names, making it difficult for students and teachers to verify or revisit the references. In contrast, the revised version follows a standardized citation format, which is the APA style. Author names are correctly abbreviated, publication years are indicated, and titles are italicized, with edition and publisher details included for printed materials. For online sources, the researcher has added article titles, source names, and retrieval dates, which not only improve traceability but also teach students the value of proper source acknowledgment.

Overall, this revision greatly improved the quality and reliability of the learning materials. By using proper citation formatting, the researcher not only strengthened the credibility of the content but also modeled good research practices for students to follow.

Research Question 4. Impact of Contextualized Learning Materials in English on the Academic Performance of Grade 8 Students

Table 9 presents the paired sample t-test results comparing the learners' pretest and post-test scores to determine if the contextualized learning material for English 8 impacts their academic performance.

Table 10*Performance of Learners as Shown in the Result of Pretest and Posttest Analysis*

	Mean	t-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Pretest	16.03				
Posttest	40.60	-27.924	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

The study measured the impact of the contextualized learning materials by comparing students' scores before and after using them. The pretest results showed an average score of 16.03, while the posttest results significantly increased to 40.60. The mean results illustrate that the posttest obtained a much higher mean score, indicating a notable improvement in the learners' performance. Likewise, the t-value (-27.924) suggests that the posttest scores are significantly higher than the pretest scores, showing a vast difference between the two. Moreover, the p-value indicates that the change between the pretest and post-test scores is statistically significant. This means that the contextualized learning material for English 8 has increased learners' academic performance after using it. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

This improvement suggests that the contextualized learning materials helped students understand their lessons more effectively. Students were more engaged and interested in learning since the content was designed to relate to their experiences and backgrounds. The materials likely made it easier for them to remember key concepts and apply what they learned. Students who see the connection between their lessons and real-life situations are more motivated to study and improve their skills. This finding aligns with the study by Lee (2021), which found that contextualized learning materials, closely connected to students' everyday experiences, significantly enhance academic performance by increasing student engagement and motivation.

Research Question 5. The Enhanced Contextualized Learning Materials Developed by the Researcher based on the Validation Made by the Respondents.

After thorough validation and revision, the enhanced contextualized learning materials for English 8 are now an excellent opportunity for teachers and students, especially since there are still concerns about students not having enough access to textbooks and other learning materials in English 8. Teachers can use these contextualized learning materials to plan lessons for the second quarter and help students slowly reach their learning objectives and competencies. What makes these items stand out is how they are put in context. It is easy for the students to understand and valuable because they use examples from their experiences. These learning materials differ from standard modules because they are based on the learners' cultures and experiences. This makes it easier for them to connect with the learning material.

It is well known that contextualized learning materials help people understand what they are reading. Gonzales (2023) shared that learning tools relevant to students' local context and experiences can make them much more interested and help them

understand. These tools allow students to connect abstract ideas with real-life applications by using things they already know from their daily lives. Localized situations can make learning material more accurate and relevant, which is especially essential for students who may have difficulty with general content (Lardizabal, 2023).

These new contextualized learning materials not only put the material in its proper setting but also make up for the long-standing lack of textbooks and other teaching materials in English 8. During the pandemic, the lessons sent out were not always relevant to the students' lives, making it harder for them to connect with and learn from the material. On the other hand, these updated materials are up-to-date and valuable because they show how schools work now and what students are going through in real life. So, they give teachers a better way to make lessons that are not only complete but also interesting and important to the lives of their students.

These better tools help students understand by giving them a structured way to learn at their own pace and addressing common comprehension problems they face. They could make a big difference in how well students understand and do in school because they align with the Department of Education's (DepEd) curriculum and standards.

These enhanced contextualized learning materials for English 8 learning tools could change how educators teach and students learn. They make up for essential resource gaps, offer material relevant to different cultures, and support the goals of the curriculum. They give teachers a powerful tool to help them teach effectively and give students learning experiences that are interesting, important, and rooted in their own lives.

Conclusions

Based on the data gathered, the developed contextualized learning materials for English 8 are highly valid, indicating that this learning resource is practical and suitable for use by Grade 8 students in their English lessons during the second quarter. The results demonstrate how well-contextualized learning resources can enhance English 8 training and address the lack of available teaching materials.

To meet the needs of students, the materials were thoroughly developed using the ADDIE model, which included clear objectives, relevant details, straightforward vocabulary, and well-structured assessments. The effectiveness of the contextualized learning materials for English was demonstrated by the validators' average weighted mean of 4.62. They commended the resources for their organization, engaging design, and alignment with learning competencies, although they also suggested a few minor modifications for future improvement.

The contextualized learning materials improved the academic performance of Grade 8 English students, as evident in the results of the paired sample t-test, which showed an increase in mean from 16.03 to 40.60. These learning resources enhanced

the students' learning experiences by incorporating cultural relevance and real-world examples. By using these contextualized learning resources, educators can improve comprehension and retention by designing relevant and meaningful content and activities in the learning materials. The developed contextualized learning materials for English 8 are a convenient alternative to traditional textbooks, improving learners' academic performance. According to this study, contextualized learning resources significantly increase student engagement, comprehension, and academic success.

Recommendations

The study's findings and conclusions suggest the following recommendations:

1. Consideration for Curriculum Use

School administrators and curriculum planners may consider the contextualized learning materials for English 8 as potential supplementary resources for second-quarter instruction. However, their official adoption is advised only after undergoing complete quality assurance procedures, including content, language, and field evaluation.

2. Preliminary Teacher Orientation

English teachers may be gradually introduced to the contextualized learning materials through initial orientation or workshops. This can help gather feedback for further revisions while also exploring how the materials might be integrated into future classroom instruction.

3. Encouraging Responsible Student Use

Students may be encouraged to explore the materials for additional practice and reinforcement of second-quarter concepts. However, use should be guided by teachers, considering that the materials are still in the refinement stage and may be subject to updates.

4. Support for Further Development

Local government units and educational institutions are encouraged to support the continued development and validation of the materials, including funding for editorial improvement, quality assurance processes, and pilot testing in schools.

5. Opportunities for Further Research

Future researchers may find it beneficial to explore the use of contextualized learning materials in other subjects or grade levels. It is also recommended that subsequent studies focus on the full validation process, including field testing and review

by education specialists, to ensure quality and effectiveness before wide-scale implementation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical guidelines were carefully followed to protect the rights and well-being of all participants in this study. First, teachers, supervisors, and students were asked to consent. This meant they were informed about the study and decided to participate voluntarily. Their privacy was also protected by keeping all responses confidential and using codes instead of names to maintain anonymity.

Before conducting the research, proper authorization was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent, Public Schools District Supervisors, and school principals. This ensured that the study followed educational policies and guidelines. The researcher also paid attention to intellectual property rights by adequately citing all sources and seeking approval to use the module evaluation checklist from Salazar (2018).

Lastly, the study adhered to the non-maleficence principle by ensuring that no individuals participating in the study were harmed. The evaluation was conducted fairly and unbiased, and all feedback from participants was used to improve the learning tools. These ethical guidelines ensured that the study was conducted responsibly and honestly.

Acknowledgments

This research is a culmination of the researcher's passion for education, made possible through hard work, determination, and the support of many people to whom the researcher is truly grateful.

The researcher sincerely thanks her adviser, Dr. Susan B. Pineda, for her guidance, knowledge, and support. Her advice and encouragement were instrumental in helping the researcher complete this study.

The researcher's deepest gratitude goes to Ms. Romalyn DC. Macayaon, her statistician, for her assistance in analyzing the data. Her assistance was essential in finishing this research.

To the Committee on Oral Examination, led by Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, President of Marinduque State University, and its members, Dr. Joy S. Montejo and Ms. Jholey Rose L. Lancion, thank you for your helpful comments and suggestions. Your feedback not only improved this study but also contributed to the researcher's academic and personal growth.

The researcher is also thankful to Ms. Anna Roffel O. Lozada, her editor, for her time and effort in improving this study. Her careful editing made this research more transparent and more organized.

The researcher extends special thanks to the Marinduque State University Graduate School staff, particularly their dedicated dean, Dr. Julieta Q. Nabos, for their guidance and support throughout this academic journey.

To the Grade 8 students at Tigwi National High School, thank you for participating in this research. Your dedication and enthusiasm inspired the researcher to complete this study.

The researcher is also grateful to the respondents from other schools in the District of Torrijos for their participation. A special thank you to the English supervisor, Ms. Jelly Sore, and the master teachers who served as the validators in this study. Your support means so much to the researcher.

Thank you to the researcher's colleagues, especially the principal, Mr. Jerome S. Catamio, for encouraging and supporting her academic journey.

To the researcher's family—Nanay Jennifer, Tatay Lamberto, and her siblings—your love, encouragement, and sacrifices have given her the strength to keep going.

To her boyfriend, Mark Louie, thank you for always believing in and supporting her.

Above all, the researcher thanks Almighty God for guiding her, giving her strength, and blessing her with the support of those who helped her along this journey.

This achievement is not hers alone but a result of the kindness and support of so many people. From the bottom of her heart, thank you all.

To God be the Glory!

REFERENCES

- Aina, J. K., Ogundele, A. G., & Olanipekun, S. S. (2013). Students' proficiency in English language relationship with academic performance in science and technical education. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 1(9), 355-358.
<https://pubs.sciepub.com/education/1/9/2/index.html>
- Aguinaldo, M., & Domingo, R. (2021). Effectiveness of contextualized learning modules in mathematics education. ResearchGate. Retrieved from
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335724177_DESIGN_DEVELOPMENT_AND_IMPLEMENTATION_OF_CONTEXTUALIZED_LEARNING_MATERIALS_IN_GRADE_7_MATHEMATICS
- Baker, E. D., Hope, L., & Karandjeff, K. (2009). Contextualized teaching & learning: A faculty primer. The Center for Student Success. <https://careeraddersproject.org/docs/CTL.pdf>
- Bernardo, R. (n.d.). Parents prefer modular learning for children amid pandemic—DepEd survey. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*. <https://www.inquirer.net>
- Bloom, B. S., Engelhart, M. D., Furst, E. J., Hill, W. H., & Krathwohl, D. R. (1956). Taxonomy of educational objectives: The classification of educational goals. Handbook I: Cognitive domain. David McKay Company.
- Bringas, R. (2014). Localized instructional materials for effective teaching and learning: A pedagogical approach. ResearchGate. Retrieved from
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350108440_Contextualized_and_Localized_Teaching_as_a_Technique_in_Teaching_Basic_Statistics
- Calderon, J. F., & Gonzales, E. C. (2011). Measurement and evaluation. National Book Store. https://www.academia.edu/124893100/Measurement_And_Evaluation
- Capuyan, A. P. (2021). Effectiveness of contextualized learning activity sheets (LAS) to the performance of Grade 7 learners in science. *International Journal of Advanced*

- Multidisciplinary Studies, 1(3), 101. <https://www.ijams-bbp.net/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/AZIEL-P.-CAPUYAN.pdf>
- Campbell. (2021). The impact of formative assessment: 5 examples for student success. Turnitin. <https://www.turnitin.com/blog/the-impact-of-formative-assessment-5-examples-for-student-success>
- Claridades, M. (2017). Utilization of contextualized learning modules in grade 8 science education. ResearchGate. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348779649_Validation_and_Utilization_of_a_Developed_Contextualized_Learning_Module_for_Science_Five
- Cubillas, R. (2018). Development and assessment of OBIMs for grade 2 learners. ResearchGate. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354696635_DEVELOPMENT_AND_VALIDATION_OF_OUTCOMEBASED_INSTRUCTIONAL_MATERIALS_OBIMs_IN_MATHEMATICS_2
- Davis, B. G. (2013). Tools for teaching (2nd ed.). Jossey-Bass. Retrieved from <https://cft.vanderbilt.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/59/Tools-For-Teaching.pdf>
- Dechavez, C. F. J. (2024). Contextualizing learning: A multi-variable analysis of student characteristics, educational settings, and academic success. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 11(8), 228–243. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/bjc/journal/v11y2024i8p228-243.html>
- Denoyelles, A. (2021, September 1). Align module objectives with assessments. Center for Distributed Learning. <https://cdl.ucf.edu/align-module-objectives-with-assessments>
- Department of Education. (2019). PISA 2018 Philippine national report. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/PISA-2018-Philippine-National-Report.pdf>
- Department of Education. (2020, February 14). Sulong EduKalidad a move to innovate PH education, says Briones. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2020/02/14/sulong-edukalidad-a-move-to-innovate-ph-education-says-briones/>
- Department of Education. (2016, June 7). The learning action cell (LAC) as a K to 12 basic education program school-based continuing professional development strategy for the improvement of teaching and learning (DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016). https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/DO_s2016_035.pdf
- Department of Education. (2020, June 19). Adoption of the basic education learning continuity plan for school year 2020-2021 in the light of the COVID-19 public health emergency. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2020/06/19/june-19-2020-do-012-2020-adoption-of-the-basic-education-learning-continuity-plan-for-school-year-2020-2021-in-the-light-of-the-covid-19-public-health-emergency/>
- Department of Education. (2020, August 24). Policy guidelines for the provision of learning resources in the implementation of the basic education learning continuity plan. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/DO_s2020_018.pdf
- Department of Education. (2020, October 2). DepEd's Learning Support Aide to reinforce teachers, guide learners in distance learning. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2020/10/02/depeds-learning-support-aide-to-reinforce-teachers-guide-learners-in-distance-learning/>
- Department of Education – Schools Division Office of Baguio City. (2020, April 30). Division Memorandum No. 205, s. 2020: Development of learning resources. https://depedpines.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Division-Memorandum-No-205-s-2020-DRRM-Webinar_.pdf
- Department of Education – Cordillera Administrative Region. (2020, April 8). Regional

- Memorandum No. 91, s. 2020: Addendum to RM No. 90, s. 2020 – Development of Learning Resources and Survey on Alternative Learning Delivery Modes. https://m.depedcar.ph/sites/default/files/regionalMemos/rm_no._091_s.2020.pdf
- Department of Education. (2020). Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs): Guidelines for Implementation during the COVID-19 Pandemic. Bureau of Curriculum Development, Republic of the Philippines.
- Department of Education [DepEd]. (2020). Guidelines on the development and implementation of self-learning modules. DepEd Order No. 35, Series of 2020.
- Delos Reyes, R. B., Tongkoh, A. L., & Chavez, J. V. (2023). Transitional challenges and factors affecting English-speaking learners in learning the Filipino language. *Journal of Namibian Studies*, 33(S1), 1720-1744. <https://doi.org/10.59670/jns.v33i.3141>
- Dinoy, M. M. (2024). Effectiveness of validated contextualized learning materials to the reading performance of Grade 5 pupils in English. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies*, 4(4). https://www.ijams-bbp.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/16-IJAMS-APRIL-2024-1-10_MARIELLE-M.-DINOY.pdf
- Estremera, M., Hizon, R., & Claridades, M. (2017). Developing effective learning modules: A guide for educators. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348779649_Validation_and_Utilization_of_a_Developed_Contextualized_Learning_Module_for_Science_Five
- Gianan, J. (2016). Localized and contextualized instructional materials: Enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368291717_Contextualized_and_Localized_Science_Teaching_and_Learning_Materials_and_Its_Characteristics_to_Improve_Students'_Learning_Performance
- Givera, A. G. (2023). Development and validation of contextualized supplementary worksheets in Grade 8 English. *United International Journal for Research & Technology*, 4(7), 283–289. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7741230>
- Gonzales, R. (2023). Development and validation of contextualized and localized supplementary learning materials in Araling Panlipunan 10 [Master's thesis, University of Rizal System]. ResearchGate. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16357.20967>
- Gueta, M. F., & Janer, S. S. (2021). Effectiveness of self-learning modules in mathematics. Paper Publications. Retrieved from <https://ijmaberjournal.org/index.php/ijmaber/article/download/1140/613/>
- Izatullah, S., Nasir, R., & Gul, F. (2022). A study to examine the relationship between English language proficiency and academic achievement of students in higher education institutions. *Global Educational Studies Review*, 7(1), 164-171. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360517816_A_Study_to_Examine_the_Relationship_between_English_Language_Proficiency_and_Academic_Achievement_of_Students_in_Higher_Education_Institutions
- Jandulong, J. A. P., & Palomares, N. R. (2024). Development and validation of module in combinatorics and probability for grade 10 learners. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(6). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11547749>
- Khan, A. A. (2023). Correlation of ESP learners' cognitive, metacognitive strategies and academic achievement. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 14(2), 76–88. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1402.01>
- Kuncoro, A. (2022). Effectiveness of contextualized learning materials in improving the reading skills and comprehension of Grade 7 students. *International Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 4(2), 45-52. <https://journals.indexcopernicus.com/api/file/viewByFileId/1750471>

- Lardizabal, A. D., Bantulo, J. S., & Orias, E. E. (2023). Effectiveness of contextualized learning material in teaching Mother Tongue 3. *International Journal of Recent Research in Thesis and Dissertation*, 4(1), 26–41. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7841934>
- Lee, J. (2021). The effect of project-based learning on English writing skill for EFL learners. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 8(2), 310–324. <https://doi.org/10.33902/JPR.202423961>
- Lockee, B. B. (2019). Instructional design: The ADDIE approach. In R. E. West (Ed.), *Foundations of learning and instructional design technology* (pp. 145–154). EdTech Books. <https://edtechbooks.org/lidtfoundations/addie>
- Lopez, R. M., & Dizon, P. L. (2022). Development and validation of contextualized reading materials for Grade 8 learners in a Philippine secondary school. *Journal of Educational Media and Technology*, 10(2), 45–60.
- Lumapenet, H. T. (2022). Effectiveness of self-learning modules on students' learning in English amidst the pandemic. *Res Militaris*, 12(6), 949–953. <https://resmilitaris.net/uploads/paper/80320049bc49d8525c388a7743297353.pdf>
- Lutching, C. (2024). Self-learning modules (SLM): Its effect on the academic performance in mathematics in the new normal. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/385785649_SELF-LEARNING_MODULES_SLM_ITS_EFFECT_ON_THE_ACADEMIC_PERFORMANCE_IN_MATHEMATICS_IN_THE_NEW_NORMAL
- Macarandang, R. M. (2009). Self-instructional teaching internship module: An evaluation. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 1(1), 1–10. <https://ijlter.org/index.php/ijlter/article/download/7675/pdf>
- Manlangit, P., Paglumotan, A. M., & Sopera, S. C. (2020, October 5). Tagapagdaloy: How Filipino parents can help ensure successful modular distance learning. FlipScience. <https://www.flipscience.ph/features/tagapagdaloy-modular-distance-learning>
- Permanasari, A., & Permana, I. (2018). Development of project-based teaching materials on energy materials to improve students' science literacy. *Journal of Science Education and Practice*, 1(1), 24–34. <https://journal.unpak.ac.id/index.php/jsep/article/view/5942>
- Pacao, A. C., & Pandes, L. T. (2025). Contextualized guided-audio visual materials for Grade 8 English learners. *RSIS International Journal of Educational Research*, 4(1), 23–34. <https://rsisinternational.org/journals/ijrsi/articles/contextualized-guided-audio-visual-materials-for-grade-8-english-learners/>
- Moss, C. M., & Brookhart, S. M. (2019). Learning targets: Helping students aim for understanding in today's lesson. ASCD. <https://www.voyagersopris.com/vsl/blog/setting-the-stage-for-success-the-power-of-learning-targets>
- Nardo, M. T. B. (2017). Modular instruction enhances learner autonomy. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 5(10), 1024-1034. <https://pubs.sciepub.com/education/5/10/3/index.html>
- Office of the President of the Philippines. (2003, May 17). Executive Order No. 210: Establishing the policy to strengthen the use of the English language as a medium of instruction in the educational system. https://lawphil.net/executive/execord/eo2003/eo_210_2003.html
- Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. (1987). The 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines – Article XIV: Education, Science and Technology, Arts, Culture and Sports. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/constitutions/the-1987-constitution-of-the-republic-of-the-philippines/>

- Ogaga, G. A., & Wallace, I. (2016). Effects of instructional materials on the teaching and learning of social studies in secondary schools in Oju Local Government Area of Benue State. *International Journal of Current Research*, 8(7), 33859-33863. ResearchGate.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/305655450_EFFECTS_OF_INSTRUCTIONAL_MATERIALS_ON_THE_TEACHING_AND_LEARNING_OF_SOCIAL_STUDIES_IN_SECONDARY_SCHOOLS_IN_OJU_LOCAL_GOVERNMENT_AREA_OF_BENUE_STATE
- Perin, D. (2011). Facilitating student learning through contextualization. Community College Research Center, Teachers College, Columbia University.
<https://ccrc.tc.columbia.edu/media/k2/attachments/facilitating-learning-contextualization-working-paper.pdf>
- Quinones, M. T. (2020). DepEd clarifies blended, distance learning modalities for SY 2020-2021. Philippine Information Agency.
<https://pia.gov.ph/news/articles/1046619>
- Ramirez (2022). Reusable educational resources for developing complex thinking on open platforms. *Education and Information Technologies*. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10639-023-12316-0>
- Ramos, M. (2025, May 1). PSA study: 19M senior high school grads 'functional illiterate'. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/2057100/psa-study-19m-senior-high-school-grads-functional-illiterate>
- Republic of the Philippines. (2013, May 15). Republic Act No. 10533: Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. LawPhil Project.
https://lawphil.net/statutes/repacts/ra2013/ra_10533_2013.html
- Rico, J. A. S., & Mendoza, L. C. (2021). Assessment of the quality of self-learning modules using the best-worst method. *IAFOR*. https://papers.iafor.org/wp-content/uploads/papers/ace2021/ACE2021_60888.pdf
- Rintaningrum, R., Aldous, C., & Conway, R. (2016). I find it easy to learn English when...: Lecturers' perspective. [Paper presentation]. Jambi International Seminar on Education (JISE), Jambi, Indonesia. Retrieved from
https://www.academia.edu/38578513/I_Find_It_Easy_To_Learn_English_When_Lecture_rs_Perspective_pdf
- Rivet, A. E., & Krajcik, J. S. (2008). Contextualizing instruction: Leveraging students' prior knowledge and experiences to foster understanding of complex science concepts. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 45(1), 79–100.
https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/bitstream/handle/2027.42/57510/20203_ftp.pdf
- Rudd, R., & Honkiss, S. (2018). Analysing the correlation between English proficiency and academic performance of students in higher education institutions. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 32(1), 134-145.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1237431.pdf>
- Salazar, G. V. (2018). Design and validation of module in General Biology 1. [Unpublished master's thesis]. Marinduque State College, Marinduque, Philippines.
- Sales, M. (2020). Development and validation of a pop-up module for kindergarten education. Marinduque State College.
- Santos, A. (2020, October 6). In the Philippines, distance learning reveals the digital divide. Heinrich Böll Stiftung. <https://eu.boell.org/en/2020/10/06/philippines-distance-learning-reveals-digital-divide>
- Saro, J. M. (2023). Effectiveness of contextualized learning materials in improving the reading skills and comprehension level of the students. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 7, 435–444.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369132825_Effectiveness_of_Contextualized

Learning_Materials_in_Improving_the_Reading_Skills_and_Comprehension_Level_of_the_Students

- Torre Franca, E. (2017). Instructional modules on rational expressions and variations: Development and evaluation. *The Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 4(2), 21–28. Retrieved from <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=20982>
- UNESCO-IBE. (2024). Madagascar: Unlocking the potential of quality and contextualized education. UNESCO International Bureau of Education. <https://www.ibe.unesco.org/en/node/181>
- Varthana. (2021). Importance of visual aids in teaching and why they are preferred. Varthana. <https://varthana.com/school/why-visual-aids-are-the-most-effective-teaching-tool-today/>
- Wang, R. (2021). A study of junior high school English writing teaching based on scaffolding theory. *IRA-International Journal of Education & Multidisciplinary Studies*, 17(3), 130–142. <https://doi.org/10.21013/jems.v17.n3.p3>
- Widyastuti, S., & Susiana, S. (2019). Development of instructional materials using the ADDIE model: A systematic approach to learning design. ResearchGate. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332673086_Using_the_ADDIE_model_to_develop_learning_material_for_actuarial_mathematics
- Yongco, J. O., & Del Valle, J. M. (2022). Development and evaluation of instructional module for special program in journalism. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*, 3(4), 97–117. <https://doi.org/10.53378/352948>
-